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APPLICATION-LEVEL SWARM-BASED ORCHESTRATION ACROSS THE CLOUD-TO-EDGE CONTINUUM

D4.2 Design, development and evaluation of the Cloud-to-Edge simulator

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Abbreviations

Term	Meaning
TOSCA	Topology and Orchestration Specification for Cloud Applications
ACO	Ant Colony Optimisation

Term	Meaning
IoT	Internet of Things
WP	Work Package
SA	Swarm Agent
RA	Resource Agent
ED	Edge Device
P2P	Peer-to-Peer
QoS	Quality of Service
LR	Lead Resource
VM	Virtual Machine
PAM	Partitioning Around Medoids

Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the design, development, and evaluation of a comprehensive Cloud-to-Edge simulation environment that enables the modelling and assessment of decentralised, self-organising orchestration mechanisms within the Swarmchestrator project. Addressing the limitations of traditional centralised orchestration frameworks, Swarmchestrator adopts a swarm-based, application-centric approach to resource management across the dynamic and heterogeneous Cloud-to-Edge continuum.

The simulation environment, built upon and extending the DISSECT-CF-Fog simulator, plays a crucial role in validating the project's innovative concepts before deployment. We chose to use the DISSECT-CF-Fog simulator because it offers a flexible, modular, and energy-aware simulation environment that is well-suited for modelling complex edge, fog and cloud computing scenarios. Key achievements include:

- Extension of DISSECT-CF-Fog to support TOSCA (Topology and Orchestration Specification for Cloud Applications) for describing applications and infrastructure.
- Implementation of sophisticated models of components involved in the deployment phase, including capacity modelling, self-organisation, and dynamic connectivity.
- Development and refinement of broadcasting algorithms for efficient resource selection and allocation during application deployment.
- Integration of time-series analysis and predictive models to anticipate system behaviour during runtime, supporting dynamic task offloading decisions for more efficient resource usage.
- Implementation and evaluation of distributed algorithms based on Ant Colony Optimisation (ACO) for decentralised orchestration, demonstrating enhanced responsiveness and improved energy efficiency in managing large-scale applications.

The simulator has been evaluated using realistic scenarios inspired by real-life use cases, including high-density IoT (Internet of Things) deployments and applications running on edge devices. The results validate the effectiveness of the decentralised orchestration approach, showing reductions in deployment time, energy consumption, and operational costs, while maintaining high system performance even under increased load and complexity.

This work forms the foundation for the Digital Twin concept in the second phase of Swarmchestrator, where simulated insights and predictions will feed directly into live system management. By offering a robust and extensible simulation platform, this deliverable significantly advances the project's goals of enhancing orchestration in the Cloud-to-Edge continuum.

1. Introduction

1.1. Document Purpose

This document has been prepared in the context of WP4 “System Design, Demonstrator Specification and Simulation” and reports on and highlights the work performed during the first 18 months of the project. It focuses on the simulation environment developed to model the Swarmchestrate ecosystem in order to provide the first testbed to measure, evaluate and fine tune the advanced distributed and decentralised approaches, and algorithms proposed within the consortium. More specifically, the document presents an overview from the application point of view including TOSCA and JSON-based application description, deployment phase with swarm formation, runtime management of the application and orchestration algorithms, all simulated with the DISSECT-CF-Fog tool. The presented results lay the foundation of the Digital Twin concept to be developed in the second half of the Swarmchestrate project.

1.2. Document Structure

The sections of the deliverable at hand are organised in the following manner:

Section 2 introduces the Swarmchestrate project from simulation’s perspective, and it also discusses the scientific background and related approaches that shaped our work.

Section 3 presents the simulation of the deployment phase of application submission within the Swarmchestrate ecosystem.

Section 4 outlines a module dedicated for time series analysis to support runtime orchestration and task offloading.

Section 5 discusses the proposed distributed and decentralised orchestration approach based on swarm-based clustering techniques.

Section 6 provides the implementation details of the initial version of the TOSCA-loader module of the DISSECT-CF-Fog simulator.

Section 7 concludes the document.

2. Background

The Swarmchestrator project aims to change the paradigm on how applications are orchestrated across the highly dynamic and heterogeneous Cloud-to-Edge computing continuum. Instead of relying on traditional centralised orchestration models, which face limitations like single points of failure, bottlenecks, and inadequate responsiveness, Swarmchestrator proposes a fully decentralised, application-centric orchestration framework [4]. This framework is based on the principles of swarm computing, where self-organising and intelligent orchestration agents collaborate within dynamic and context-aware groups to manage and deploy microservices across diverse and distributed infrastructures.

A key aspect of Swarmchestrator is its application-centric perspective, which means that the orchestration is guided by the application's goals and constraints, rather than focusing purely on low-level resource optimisation. Given the complexity and diversity of Cloud-to-Edge infrastructures, standardised description languages are essential in organising and structuring the various components and requirements of applications. To this end, the project leverages and extends TOSCA, a widely adopted modelling language. TOSCA allows developers to define not only the structure and topology of applications but also their deployment, monitoring, and operational requirements in a standardised manner [5]. By enhancing TOSCA to support dynamic, decentralised orchestration in heterogeneous environments, Swarmchestrator aims to demonstrate how swarm-based distributed intelligence, paired with robust description languages, can fundamentally reshape application management in the Cloud-to-Edge continuum.

Due to the complexity of the Swarmchestrator orchestration solution, a digital twin and simulation environment are being developed in parallel with the actual implementation to model decentralised, self-organising orchestration services. Regarding the simulation, it is developed by extending an existing tool, namely DISSECT-CF-Fog [6], which provides the first testbed to measure and evaluate the effectiveness of the project's solutions. The simulator is a discrete-event, open-source tool initially designed for modelling IoT-Fog-Cloud environments. It supports the detailed representation of both physical and virtual resources, such as cloud datacentres and fog nodes, along with their energy consumption and network characteristics.

Furthermore, its capabilities include simulating IoT applications, modelling IoT devices and sensors, and calculating both IoT and cloud costs based on real-world provider pricing schemes. Thanks to its modular structure, the simulator provides a stable basis for modelling Swarmchestrator-defined messaging protocols, application behaviours, and components, thereby making it a suitable choice for the extension required to meet the modelling needs of the Swarmchestrator ecosystem.

This extended simulator towards the Cloud-to-Edge continuum is used to simulate various scenarios, assessing energy consumption, execution time, data processing, and overall system efficiency of the decentralised orchestration. The outcomes of these evaluations then are fed back into the development process, supporting the refinement of technical solutions and guiding the deployment process.

More specifically, the simulator will be further extended in three directions as part of the project:

- To incorporate support for TOSCA-based application descriptions, enabling the simulator to parse and execute application models directly from standardised specifications. This ensures alignment between the simulation environment and the actual deployment workflows, and facilitates seamless testing, validation, and refinement of orchestration strategies based on real-world TOSCA definitions.
- To model distributed, self-organising Swarmchestrator services, allowing for extensive experimentation and fine-tuning of the developed algorithms without the need for repeating the evaluation scenarios in a real-world testbed.
- To evolve into a digital twin that operates in parallel with the live Swarmchestrator ecosystem, leveraging predictive algorithms and simulated outputs to dynamically adjust system parameters at runtime.

To adapt the envisioned Swarmchestrator universe into the existing simulation environment, we primarily focus on the implementation of several constructs introduced within the scope of the Swarmchestrator project, such as the capacity providers, Resource Agents (RAs), Swarm Agents (SAs), Edge Devices (EDs) and application descriptions. All of these are discussed in more detail in D2.1. Nevertheless, behaviour of further components such as the Knowledge Management (as detailed in D3.1) are planned to be mirrored for the simulation environment.

2.1. Related Work

Over the past decade, numerous Cloud-to-Edge simulators have been introduced to realistically model the behaviour and functionality of complex systems. As a result, selecting the most suitable tool for a given research objective can be a challenging task. Furthermore, these simulators vary significantly in terms of their level of granularity. Fine-grained simulations typically offer highly precise and detailed modelling of individual components, aiming for maximum reliability, often at the expense of scalability. In contrast, coarse-grained simulators prioritise scalability, enabling the modelling of a large number of components over extended periods of simulated time. This makes them particularly well-suited for simulating more extreme scenarios, where they can serve as essential building blocks in research.

Another important aspect to consider is the intended purpose of the simulator. General-purpose tools are capable of modelling a wide range of functionalities, though this often involves abstracting certain features and behaviours. On the other hand, domain-specific simulators tend to concentrate on a narrower set of layers or functionalities, providing significantly more detail within their focus area.

Over the years, several research efforts have aimed to provide a comprehensive analysis of Cloud-to-Edge simulators. For instance, in [7], a survey and taxonomy covering 44 cloud, fog, and IoT simulators was presented, highlighting their differences and the ways in which they model system components. Similarly, [8] offered a more focused study of 24 edge simulation

solutions, evaluating them based on criteria such as functionality, maintainability, scalability, reliability, efficiency, and usability.

Among the publicly available simulators, FogTorchII [9] explores deployment strategies for application components on fog architectures using a Monte Carlo-based approach. However, this simulator lacks detailed modelling of fog and IoT layers, which limits its applicability in certain research scenarios. YAFS [10] is one of the more recent simulators, offering various functionalities and supporting multiple research objectives such as application module placement and message routing policies. Despite its flexibility, it entirely omits the virtualisation layer from its architecture model.

Similarly, FogNetSim++ [11] does not include a dedicated layer for modelling virtualised resources or actuators. Instead, it places strong emphasis on detailed network operations and their characteristics. As a typical network-centric simulator, it focuses on communication protocols such as HTTP and MQTT.

A number of simulators have been developed on top of the well-known CloudSim platform. Since these simulators rely on different versions of CloudSim and extend different sets of modules, interoperability among them is not feasible. The most representative tools built on this foundation include iFogSim [12], MobFogSim [13], EdgeCloudSim [14], and IoTsim-Edge [15].

However, most aforementioned solutions suffer from at least one of three shortcomings:

- *Limited scope and features.* Many tools target only a single aspect (e.g. FogTorchII focuses solely on cost-aware deployment; iFogSim only supports static, tree-like topologies; EdgeCloudSim considers WLAN/WAN but omits network topology and energy models) [7, 8].
- *Maintenance and usability.* Several simulators have not been updated for years, implying missing, needed and unimplemented features (e.g., FogNetSim++) [8].
- *Non-functional quality.* It is hindered by the lack of modularity in extensions such as energy, cost, and mobility. Many simulators require these extensions to be manually integrated, rather than supporting them directly (e.g., FogTorchII, iFogSim, EdgeCloudSim, PureEdgeSim) [7, 8].

On the other hand, DISSECT–CF-Fog provides a balanced, up-to date simulation platform combining the following characteristics:

- *Use cases.* The simulator supports cloud computing, fog computing and IoT workflow simulations [6].
- *Unified modelling.* The simulator discrete-event core handles both virtual machine lifecycles and packet-level network transfers under a single engine [7, 8].
- *Rich energy and cost modelling.* The simulator manages energy meters (e.g., per CPU, disk) plus real-world pricing models for Cloud-to-Edge tiers, aligned with commercial (e.g., AWS, Azure, IBM) or customised schemes [6, 7].

- *Cloud-to-Edge extensibility.* The simulator uses XML-driven scenario descriptors for devices, sensors (e.g., measurement times, data rates), and multi-tier topologies, requiring minimal Java coding to define complex experiments [6, 8].
- *Active Development.* Beyond the DISSECT-CF-Fog core functionalities, the simulator is actively maintained and updated, ensuring long-term viability [6, 7, 8].

Therefore, these considerations motivated the selection of DISSECT-CF-Fog as the simulation platform for Swarmchestr. It is a fine-grained yet scalable and general-purpose simulator, which ensures a reliable and extensible framework for exploring decentralised, swarm-inspired behaviours. Compared to existing solutions, this simulation tool has already been extended in the following directions:

- *Hybrid, application-centric architecture.* To combine a two-layer hierarchical structure (an interface layer of dynamic RAs and per-application SA networks) with a fully P2P (Peer-to-Peer) operational model. The designed interface layer should discover resources on demand, while SAs manage each application's lifecycle in a decentralised, self-organising manner [1].
- *Enhanced predictive decision-making.* By integrating time-series analysis with a fuzzy-based Pliant data-offloading algorithm, enriching prediction with multiple input models and historical context [2].
- *Overlapping ACO clustering.* Building on the fog colony concept, to introduce a centralised ACO clustering algorithm alongside a decentralised, task-triggered grouping mechanism. This dual approach flexibly allocates resources across heterogeneous, dynamic environments without requiring predefined clusters [3] in order to find suitable resources for application execution.
- *Declarative modelling based on TOSCA.* Extending DISSECT-CF-Fog with TOSCA-based application parsing and orchestration modules. This unified simulation platform enables rigorous and repeatable evaluation of fully decentralised, application-centric strategies before deployment in real-world Cloud-to-Edge infrastructures.

All these approaches will be detailed in the following sections.

3. Simulation of the Deployment Phase

In this section, our aim is to validate the proposed application deployment strategy of Swarmchestr, which was defined in D2.1. First, we provide a detailed description of modelling capacity providers, RAs, SAs, EDs and applications in the extended DISSECT-CF-Fog simulator. The results presented in this section have been summarised in a research paper accepted for presentation at the ICFEC 2025 conference [1]. The valuable insights gained from this extended simulation tool also guide the implementation of Swarmchestr.

The purpose of the interconnected RAs is to represent the capacities of various resource providers and to provide an interface for application submissions. As a resource, any physical components (e.g., Raspberry Pis, physical machines of the edge, fog and cloud nodes) or dynamically created virtual components (e.g., virtual machines) are considered. Capacities

are logical groupings of the previously mentioned resources that are available for application components.

These capacities of resources are offered every time when an application is submitted to the orchestration system. For this, a resource selection process is executed to identify the optimal set of resources based on the application QoS (Quality of Service) goals. In this set, the most suitable resource (e.g., that provides the most CPU cores) named Lead Resource (LR), will host the Kubernetes control component. The control service at this point will solely launch the SA that will complete the deployment by initiating the required resources for the application components.

3.1. DISSECT-CF-Fog

DISSECT-CF-Fog is a direct extension of the DISSECT-CF simulator [16]. This core simulation framework primarily supports research on infrastructure-level cloud schedulers. Compared to most similar simulation tools, DISSECT-CF offers two key advantages: a unified resource sharing model and a more advanced IaaS stack simulation with the fine-grained modelling of physical and virtual machines, storage, and internal data centre networking.

DISSECT-CF-Fog has been in development since 2016, evolving through five major stages to reach its current capabilities.

1. The *IoT module* was developed to facilitate the modelling of IoT infrastructures, focusing on flexibility and ease of configuration for devices and sensors.
2. The *Fog module* introduced both the physical and logical components of fog-based infrastructures into the simulator.
3. The *Actuator and Mobility module* enables bidirectional communication between simulation nodes and IoT actuators, while also supporting mobility for physical entities through a geographic coordinate system and various movement policies.
4. The *Energy Metering module* enhances the IoT model with energy monitoring capabilities, made possible through microcontroller-level modelling.
5. Finally, the *Workflow module* introduces support for analysing stream processing scenarios, complementing the previously available batch-processing functionality.

The modules of both the core simulator and the extended DISSECT-CF-Fog build upon one another, as it can be seen in Figure 1. The *Event System* manages both recurring and delayed events and controls the overall system state throughout the simulation utilising the DES system. The *Energy Modelling* subsystem enables the monitoring of energy consumption across all simulated resources, considering linear and static energy consumption models, which can be mapped to the different states of the components.

The *Unified Resource Sharing* subsystem introduces resource spreader components that act as central coordinators for resource provisioning. Instead of letting individual components manage their resources independently, this approach enables consistent and fair allocation, particularly of bandwidth and computing resources, by allowing shared behaviour across lower-level computing abstractions.

The *Infrastructure Simulation* subsystem handles the modelling of physical machines, virtual machines, IoT-related components, networking, and storage. Above this layer, the *Cost Modelling* subsystem provides detailed modules for calculating pricing on both the IoT and Cloud sides, tailored to various providers. The *Infrastructure Management* subsystem offers IaaS components, including physical and virtual machine schedulers, and workflow job schedulers. In addition, this layer is also responsible for representing fog layers.

At the top layer, the *Fog Logical Management* subsystem focuses exclusively on fog and IoT-related components. It includes logical controllers responsible for managing IoT applications, actuators, and mobile devices, and offers a comprehensive view of potential strategies applicable to these elements.

Figure 1. The architecture of the DISSECT-CF-Fog simulator with the main components

3.2. Application Description Format

Given the ongoing development of TOSCA description format in WP2 for the targeted applications, we first chose to adopt a custom JSON-based format to support the ongoing system development with the simulator. Once the final version of TOSCA used in Swarmchestrator is published, thanks to parallel developments (see in Section 6), the existing modules of the simulator can easily be tailored to the new format.

Swarmchestrator supports microservices-based applications consisting of multiple deployable components. In the application description file used for simulation, as illustrated in Figure 2, the application owner must first define the QoS goals, represented as key-value pairs that specify requirements. Currently, we consider four types of QoS attributes: energy, price, latency, and bandwidth. As shown in Line 3-6 of Figure 2, each value ranges from 0 to 1 and indicates how important the given QoS metric is for the application owner.

Then, the component specification follows, listing each application component along with its type. The *compute* type includes a container image for instantiation, while the *storage* type refers to a partition that needs to be allocated. For instance, the size of the image file for application component *Comp-1* is 1 GB, as defined in Line 8, while *Comp-2* in Line 9 refers to a storage type with no further characteristics.

The third part specifies various resource requirements, detailing the needs of application components in terms of hardware limits (CPU, RAM, and/or storage), the number of instances, the cloud provider hosting the component, and the physical region. It is worth mentioning that these parameters are optional. For example, resource requirement *Res-1* needs 4 CPU cores and 4 GB of memory for each of its 3 instances. In addition, these instances must be provided by AWS and located in Europe, as shown in Line 12. For *Res-2*, only the size of the reserved partition needs to be defined, which is 100 GB in this case, as shown in Line 13.

Lastly, the component and resource specifications must be mapped to apply the defined resource requirements to the respective components, as shown in Line 16 and 17 of Figure 2. This structural separation ensures the reusability of resource requirements when multiple application components are defined.

To fasten the evaluation phase, a JSON-based application generator was implemented in the DISSECT-CF-Fog simulator, which takes into account the aforementioned structure with the required parameters, enabling the rapid creation of arbitrary number of application instances with customisable parameters.

```

1- {
2   "name": "App-1",
3   "energyPriority": 0.7,
4   "pricePriority": 0.7,
5   "latencyPriority": 0.3,
6   "bandwidthPriority": 0.3,
7-  "components": [
8     {"name": "Comp-1", "image": "1073741824", "type": "compute"},
9     {"name": "Comp-2", "type": "storage"}
10  ],
11-  "resources": [
12    {"name": "Res-1", "cpu": "4", "memory": "4294967296", "instances": "3", "provider": "AWS", "location": "EU"},
13    {"name": "Res-2", "size": "107374182400"}
14  ],
15-  "mapping": [
16    {"component": "Comp-1", "resource": "Res-1"},
17    {"component": "Comp-2", "resource": "Res-2"}
18  ]
19 }

```

Figure 2. An example application in JSON format for simulation

3.3. Resource Agent and Capacity Model

The RA, in simulation, is modelled as a lightweight virtualised resource utilising the underlying physical infrastructure. To define an RA, it is first necessary to specify the capacities it provides for the application components. In the simulator, capacities are currently represented by a tuple consisting of CPU, memory, and storage attributes of the corresponding physical resource (e.g., cloud or fog/edge node). Then, each RA is associated with a price value that defines the hourly usage cost of the given capacity in a pay-as-you-go manner. Finally, the RA requires a strategy that defines how it generates offers every time an application request is received.

Currently, two strategies are implemented, namely *first-fit* and *first-fit-decreasing*, which define the logic for mapping application requirements to the available capacities. The *first-fit* algorithm sorts application components based on their CPU and then their storage size requirements in increasing order, then it maps those one-by-one on the available capacities. However, if all RAs apply the same logic for matchmaking, it could result in failure to cover each application component adequately. To mitigate this, agents can start their mapping process with the component requiring the highest number of CPU cores realising *first-fit-decreasing*. Optionally, a third strategy can also be applied: agents can sort the application components randomly before applying matchmaking to introduce variability.

3.4. Edge Device Model

Although the simulator was originally designed to comprehensively model IoT-Fog-Cloud systems, the implementation only supported to model the general behaviour of EDs. To refine the simulation and fully reflect the dynamic nature of edge devices for Swarmchestrator, we enhanced the model to better distinguish between capacity levels, where capacities closer to the upper bound represent cloud-like behaviour, while those near the lower bound models edge characteristics. Thanks to the flexible and modular design of the simulation tool, these enhancements allow a more accurate and adaptive representation of edge devices. This means locally available processing capabilities and the edge device mobility support, reflecting the dynamic connectivity and availability typical of edge

environments. Further details of the refined edge model of the DISSECT-CF-Fog simulator related to the runtime management can be found in Section 4.2.

3.5. The Broadcasting Algorithm

When an application is submitted to the Swarmchestrator universe, one of the RAs considered as a gateway or lead RA, will be responsible for initiating and managing the deployment phase. Its first task is to find a suitable group of resources with capacities for the application, thus, to collect all suitable groups fulfilling the requirements of the particular application, a broadcasting algorithm is executed. The output is the possible resource offers.

In the early stage of the project, a recursive algorithm was envisioned to obtain these possible resource offers. Figure 3 illustrates a working example of this recursive algorithm. As can be seen on this figure, the resource requirements (A, B, C, D) are broadcasted to all available RAs asking for their coverage of the required resources. The coverage for each RA can be set as follows:

- Partial coverage: RA-1 can only fulfil requirements C and D, thus, the broadcasting continues to all other RAs to look for the remaining resources A and B.
- Full coverage: RA-2 can fulfil all the resources, thus, no need to further continue the search on that path.
- Zero coverage: RA-X cannot fulfil any of the requirements, thus, no need to further continue the search on that path either.

Figure 3. Initial version of the broadcasting algorithm

It is worth mentioning that for a given application, the execution of this broadcasting algorithm results in receiving the same application requirements with different coverage over and over again. The reason for this behaviour is that RAs were envisioned as intelligent components that are interacting and competing with each other to cover as many application components as they can. However, this message strategy can generate a huge amount of messages even for a relatively small number of RAs. Furthermore, the gateway RA needs to know when the broadcasting algorithm terminated on the last active path, and it also needs to collect each of the offers to choose the best for the given QoS requirements. To propagate these pieces of information towards the gateway RA, new, so-called

acknowledgement messages have to be introduced, which consequently means that the number of the total messages keeps growing.

To show the performance of the aforementioned message strategy, we implemented the broadcasting algorithm in the DISSECT-CF-Fog simulator with the following parameters:

- The initial RA was randomly selected.
- The size of the broadcasting (BCAST) and acknowledgement (ACK) messages was set to 100 and 50 bytes, respectively.
- The latency among the RAs was set between 50 - 100 ms, and the bandwidth was set to 100 Mbps.
- Only one application was submitted with 3 types of requirements.
- The capacities of RAs were set randomly to fulfil the application's requirements.

The results can be seen in Table 1. It is worth noting that no other messages such as communication between the already deployed components were simulated on the network. *Time* reflects the total length of executing the broadcasting, *No. of solutions* shows how many full coverages were found, *Total message size* reflects the network usages of the broadcasting algorithm, while *Total message count* shows the number of messages that were needed to find the aforementioned solutions. Lastly, the *Worst case* of messaging is also calculated when each RA is able to fulfil only one application requirement resulting in an exponentially growing number of messages.

No. of RAs	6	8	10	12
Time (ms)	240	536	656	1,060
No. of solutions	4	6	13	18
Total message size (MB)	~ 0.001	~ 0.22	~ 1.5	~ 15
Total message count (BCAST)	27 (9)	3,471 (1,157)	24,315 (8,105)	239,163 (79,721)
Worst case (BCAST / ACK)	325 / 650	13,699 / 27,398	986,409	108,505,111

Table 1. Results of the initial version of the broadcasting algorithm

The outputs clearly show that this type of broadcasting results in a huge search space and generates too many messages. Although with the randomly chosen parameters the worst-case scenario for messaging was never reached, it could occur if the number of application components equals the number of RAs and each RA is able to provide capacity for exactly one application component.

3.6. The Refined Version of the Broadcasting Algorithm

To reduce the communication complexity, a refined algorithm was proposed for collecting offers. As shown in Figure 4, RA-X broadcasts the application requirements to all available RAs, requesting offers. Each receiving RA determines its coverage and responds with it to RA-X. Then RA-X compiles unique groups of possible offers and ranks them (according to the ranking algorithm presented in details in D1.1), and picks the first offer that maximises the chances of fulfilling the QoS goals for the submitted application. The Python script of the ranking algorithm is called by the simulation via subprocessing.

Figure 4. The refined broadcasting with acknowledgment messages

To avoid conflicts in reserving capacities, when simultaneously multiple applications are submitted (Step 0 in Figure 3) to be deployed, a state transition is introduced as it is shown in Figure 5 with the states of *Free*, *Reserved*, *Assigned*, and *Allocated*. The stage changes must be atomic to avoid the race condition of the capacities. These state transitions are implicitly presented in Figure 4 as well:

- Step 1 to Step 2: The state of capacities offered for the given application are set from *Free* to *Reserved*.
- Step 2 to Step 3: The state of capacities belonging to the winning offer are set from *Reserved* to *Allocated*, while the rest of the *Reserved* capacities for the given application are set back to *Free*.

In case of any failure, the gateway RA in Step 4 in Figure 4 will be aware of the issue based on the acknowledgements it received and the gateway RA can proceed accordingly. It can

choose the second best offer or start another round of broadcasting to collect new offers. In the implementation, we chose the latter for every RA in the system.

Figure 5. State transition graph for managing capacities

Figure 6 illustrates the main components, which will be simulated in DISSECT-CF-Fog to model the deployment phase of Swarmchestrator. As it can be seen in this figure, two providers (i.e., Cloud-1 and Cloud-2 in this case) are available, which provide CPU, memory and storage capacities for three RAs that are connected via a P2P network. These RA services are hosted on these cloud nodes, representing and providing the remaining part of the underlying resource for application components. To show the flexible configuration of the RAs, it is allowed to provide partial capacities or capacities from different vendors. In this example, RA-1 cannot offer any storage-related capacities. On the other hand, RA-2 provides capacities both from Cloud-1 and Cloud-2.

Cloud-1 is also responsible for providing (i.e., hosting) a Docker Hub-like image registry service and the application components come with different requirements fulfilled by different RA. It is worth mentioning that these applications are simulated components, no real database or server operations are executed.

Figure 6. An example architecture of the modelled Swarmchestrator system in DISSECT-CF-Fog

3.7. Results

This section presents the outcomes of the simulation experiments conducted to assess the performance and behaviour of the proposed system under various conditions. The simulator receives application descriptions using the format described in Section 3.2. During the evaluation the applications with different specifications are simultaneously submitted to evaluate the system’s performance. Table 2 presents the ranges used for the specification of each application. The measurements were conducted using a PC equipped with Intel Core i7-3770 CPU @ 3.40GHz, 23 GB RAM and Ubuntu 20.04 operating systems.

No. of components	compute: 3, storage: 1
Required CPU (pc.)	min: 1, max: 6
Required RAM (GB)	min: 1, max: 6
Required Storage (GB)	min: 1, max: 10
Image size (MB)	min: 1, max: 500
Required instances	min: 1, max: 3
Message size (KB)	2

Table 2. Experimental settings for the applications

The RA, as it was mentioned earlier, is modelled as a lightweight virtualised resource, utilising 1 CPU core and 1 GB of memory of the underlying physical resource in the simulator. The physical resources in simulation mimic the behaviour of capacities (discussed

in Section 3.3). The capacities in simulation environments for our experiments are created from the interval-based specification presented in Table 3.

Location	EU, US
Provider	AWS, Azure
CPU (pc.)	min: 16, max: 100
RAM (GB)	min: 16, max: 100
Idle power (W)	min: 150, max: 225
Max power (W)	min: 500, max: 3500
Bandwidth (Mbps)	min: 50, max: 1200
Latency (ms)	min: 15, max: 100
Price (EUR/hour)	min: 0.025, max: 25

Table 3. Experimental settings for the capacities of nodes

A capacity with properties closer to the upper bound is considered cloud-based, and closer towards the lower bound is imitating edge-based nodes. The RAs are hosted by these nodes, representing and providing the remaining part of the underlying resource for application components. For our experimentation, the infrastructure consisted of 8 capacities each represented by one RA, jointly forming a network of 8 RAs.

When an application is submitted, the network randomly assigns an RA to manage the deployment. The assigned gateway RA broadcasts the request to all RAs. Every RA evaluates the request by matching application components to its available capacity using a first-fit strategy, where components are sorted by CPU requirements, with 50% of RAs sorting it in ascending order and the rest in descending order. The RA maps as many components as its capacity permits. This mixed sorting strategy helps us avoid scenarios, where only components with higher CPU requirements are mapped to capacities. When the gateway RA receives all responses (including its own), containing RA-application component pairs, it generates offers by creating all unique combinations of these pairs, ensuring each application component is included exactly once in each combination. These pairs constitute all possible offers that can fulfil the requirements of submitted application.

Next, two different resource selection algorithms are implemented to evaluate the obtained resource offers by ranking them in accordance to the QoS attributes (latency, cost, bandwidth, energy) and their priorities as defined in the application description. In addition, the reliability of each resource offer is also taken into account. The implemented resource selection algorithms are labelled as Cost and Borda, where their formal description and details are discussed in D1.1. The Cost method computes a total cost by normalising and

weighting these attributes, while Borda assigns scores per attribute based on ranks and priorities. In this current implementation, the input parameters (e.g., the bandwidth or the energy values of the capacity providers) are provided by the DISSECT-CF-Fog simulator.

The first offer in the ranked list is the winning group consisting of pairs of RA and application components. The next step involves the selection of the LR by RA-X to host the SA. For this experimentation, we consider the application component with higher CPU cores as the criterion for LR. Furthermore, to mimic realistic behaviour, we also set up a Docker Hub-like image registry to store the container images of the application components with 1000 Mbps bandwidth in the DISSECT-CF-Fog simulator. Once the LR is selected, the image files are transferred over the network where the application components are deployed. Though the primary goal of this work is to mimic the deployment phase, we also emphasise the long-term impact of the deployment decision by employing a 30-minute task of each deployed *compute* component to utilise the allocated CPU cores fully.

The evaluation examined the ability of Swarmchestrator to handle the simultaneous submission of six applications, with an emphasis on varying priority levels of QoS attributes. We evaluated six strategies: a randomly selected offer, one with equal priorities, and four where a single QoS attribute had a priority of 1.0 while the others were set to 0.1. For comparison, the following metrics are considered: *Simulation Time*, the time from the application submission to the last task's completion, *Total Price*, the resource costs based on hourly provider rates; *Avg. Deployment Time*, the time from submission to component deployment influenced by latency and bandwidth; and *Total Energy*, the aggregated energy consumption per node during the *Simulation Time*.

The results are shown in Table 4, where the best values are highlighted in green and the worst in red for each metric, demonstrating the performance of the Borda and Cost approaches. In cases where a priority value of 1.0 was assigned (rows 1-8) to all applications, the proposed ranking algorithm consistently performed better, as indicated by the green columns. For example, a price-aware strategy can result in the minimisation of operating costs, the energy-aware strategy can provide the minimum energy consumption, and the bandwidth-aware policy was able to minimise the average deployment time and, consequently, the overall simulation time. However, since the goal was to simulate the deployment phase of Swarmchestrator, latency plays a pivotal role in communication between components during runtime; therefore, the latency-aware strategy had no visible effect on deployment, as expected.

In terms of approaches, the Cost method, though it yields the worst results (red cells), generally outperforms the Borda method in achieving the best priority-specific values. The only exception is the price-aware strategy, in which case the Cost method still provides the second-best value. The Equal method balances cost and deployment efficiency, while the Random strategy shows that unsystematic selection of resource configurations can lead to suboptimal outcomes across all metrics.

Priority	Method	Simulation Time (min)	Total Price (EUR)	Avg. Deployment Time (min)	Total Energy (KWh)
Energy	Borda	37.946	0.053	3.636	2.232
	Cost	37.946	0.046	3.779	2.170
Price	Borda	35.044	0.015	2.451	2.292
	Cost	37.946	0.032	3.645	2.211
Latency	Borda	34.641	0.077	1.352	2.360
	Cost	34.562	0.079	1.285	2.363
Bandwidth	Borda	34.385	0.075	1.288	2.316
	Cost	32.175	0.115	0.968	2.260
Equal	Borda	34.318	0.036	1.620	2.229
	Cost	34.562	0.076	1.285	2.363
Random		34.437	0.082	1.365	2.310

Table 4. Simulation results for different priorities and resource selection methods

More specifically on energy usage, Figure 7 and 8 show the accumulated energy consumption per node recorded during the energy and latency-aware scenarios. The measurement is for the time from the application submission to the completion of all tasks and does not include the cold start and initial infrastructure setup. In the case of the energy-aware approach, the CPU-heavy tasks start after the fifth minute, while the latency-aware strategy results in faster application deployment (as it is shown by Avg. Deployment Time in Table 4 as well), thus the related tasks already start after the third minute.

It can also be observed that the ranking algorithm selected the same nodes for the simultaneously submitted applications in each case (node-1, node-4, and node-5 for the energy-aware strategy and node-3, node-4, and node-6 for the bandwidth-aware strategy). Based on this, we can conclude that applications with similar QoS priorities can create bottlenecks for the selected nodes during runtime.

Figure 7. The energy consumption per node with energy priority

Figure 8. The energy consumption per node with latency priority

4. Simulation of the Runtime Phase

Distributed architectures such as edge and fog computing, commonly used together with IoT applications, present significant challenges in resource management. Such Cloud-to-Edge systems often consist of a vast number of devices including sensors, actuators, smart devices, and computing nodes. Managing the resulting data of these systems efficiently and ensuring sufficient computing capacity and low latency are crucial, particularly for time-critical applications.

A central challenge in these environments is determining where and how to offload computational tasks. Efficient offloading strategies are essential to balance execution cost, energy consumption, and system performance, especially when dealing with resource-constrained edge and fog nodes. Within this context, time-series analysis plays a pivotal role by enabling proactive predictions of key system metrics, such as computational load, latency, and potential failures. These forecasts inform and enhance offloading decisions, ensuring that tasks are allocated not only based on current system states but also on anticipated conditions. This predictive approach is critical for maintaining high QoS and system resilience in complex, dynamic environments.

By integrating predictive models into the decision-making process of the DISSECT-CF-Fog simulator, Swarmchestrator could facilitate smarter runtime adaptation by anticipating system demands to optimise resource utilisation. For this purpose, we implemented a highly flexible module capable of performing time-series analysis to predict key features of the underlying infrastructure and the hosted applications. The achieved results are also summarised and published in [2].

4.1 Time-series Analysis to Support Offloading

Our solution adopts a decentralised approach for task reassignment, designed to align with Swarmchestrator's decision-making perspective and to be reusable within its framework, particularly in scenarios requiring adaptive and autonomous runtime behaviour. The

simulator's decentralised decision-makers, which determine to which adjacent node the task should be reassigned, are able to deal with naive and sophisticated approaches. While the architecture in this solution does not implement the full Swarmchestrator concept, given its adoption of a multi-layered fog-cloud topology, it maintains the flexibility to form swarms or clusters. These clusters can establish hierarchical relationships, enabling communication and coordination not only within swarms but also between them. This layered approach combines the advantages of decentralised decision-making with the scalability and structure necessary for complex, distributed environments.

In the hierarchical network of computing nodes, services running on overloaded nodes can offload tasks to other nodes. These nodes may operate at the same layer (referred to as neighbours), or nodes in higher layers (referred to as parents) in a fog-to-cloud topology. To support this offloading mechanism, we define policies (i.e., strategies) that determine how the target node for task reassignment is selected. The *Hold Down* strategy only considers neighbours and omits the parent node, thus it keeps the tasks in a fog layer as low as possible. Meanwhile, *Push Up* omits the neighbours and always sends the data to upper layers. These strategies leverage one of the trade-offs of a multi-layered fog topology: the higher layer a task is processed, the stronger resources can be utilised to get faster processing as well. However, the lower layer a task is processed, the less computational cost can be expected since weaker resources are sold cheaper.

A more sophisticated strategy, namely *Pliant*, which is based on fuzzy logic [17]. For each reachable fog and cloud node a score is calculated. The first step is data normalisation to the $[0,1]$ interval with a Sigmoid function, which is one of the most popular threshold functions. If the normalised value is close to 1 that means that it is a more valuable property. We might want to modify the importance of the value. If this value is greater or smaller than our expectation, we use the Kappa function for such a purpose, which is also a Sigmoid-like function. The next step is to merge these values applying different kinds of operators in continuous value logic: conjunctive, disjunctive, and aggregative. Finally, the score value is rounded to an integer number that represents the probability of the different alternative nodes. Using these score values as probabilities for each node, we randomly choose the one where the task will be migrated.

To make time series analysis available in the DISSECT-CF-Fog simulator, we used the *Scikit-learn* library, which provides various data analysis methods, and ML-algorithms. *Tensorflow* was also involved, which is a framework for machine learning and artificial intelligence and used to train and deduce a deep neural network.

To add the predicted parameters to the Pliant algorithm during decision making, we first need data pre-processing. The original data is denoted with light yellow colour in Figure 9. This step is necessary because ML and neural network models can more easily learn the characteristics and patterns of the data, if they are uniform and placed between a certain interval, thus we normalise the data to the $[0,1]$ interval. We can also observe that the data follow a stepwise pattern. Usually it is difficult to create a predictor for such a pattern, thus we used one of the well-known smoothing techniques called the Savitzky-Golay method [18]. This procedure goes through the dataset using a window with a given width, then an

n -degree polynomial fit is performed at the centre of each window. As a result of preprocessing, the data series are simpler with minimal noise, but the main features and patterns remain.

Figure 9. The prediction of the unprocessed data for the given node with error metrics

To predict the possible future value of any feature, the simulator waits for the predefined number of measurements (e.g. 256 input values to the prediction). In this case, the yellow line in the diagram in Figure 9 denotes the size of the not yet processed data for the particular computing node. When the required amount of samples is available, the 256-length list is divided into a training and test dataset at a ratio of 0.75-0.25% (as shown with dashed vertical lines in Figure 9). Whenever the measurement-list is updated, the earliest information is removed from the list (i.e. it follows the FIFO-logic), thus in every iteration, the training and test database are also updated accordingly. To measure how accurately a predictor forecast the test data based on the training data, which denoted with blue in Figure 9, we applied the following error metrics: Mean Absolute Error (MAE), Mean Square Error (MSE) and Root Mean Square Error (RMSE).

Then on the full 256-length dataset, the predictor makes a forecasting again, and the predicted future values with the formerly measured error metrics are forwarded to the Pliant-based decision maker. The results of the actual 64-length predictions are visually represented with red in Figure 9 with the actual error metrics, which are the outputs of the prediction. The amount of the not yet processed data (i.e. unprocessed data) is predicted for each computing node separately in a decentralised fashion. In the predictor framework, we implemented six different kinds of prediction algorithm which are the following:

- The three-component ARIMA is a statistical model and is a type of regression analysis to predict the upcoming points of a series, which comes with three input parameters. Component AR with parameter p represents the order of autoregression, which is the number of lagged observations to be used (lag is a fixed amount of passing time). To use ARIMA more effectively, module I with parameter d makes the time series stationary, which means that the mean and variance of the series remain constant. The difference between the data values and the previous values is taken d -times until the original series becomes stationary. Finally, component MA with parameter q is

the moving average, it denotes the correlation between the current value of the time series and past forecasting errors. q is the size of the moving average window.

- Another popular procedure to foresee is the Holt-Winter's (HW) Method, which is able to consider the average, trends, and seasonality of the dataset, because it is not a standalone method, but the combination of three: Simple Exponential Smoothing (SES), Holt's Exponential Smoothing (HES) and Winter's Exponential Smoothing (WES). SES is only ideal if the data contain no seasonality and trends, because this part only focuses on the average of recent periods. It comes with the parameter *alpha*, which is the smoothing coefficient between 0 and 1. If the value is close to 1, it means the more recent members of the series are taken into account, otherwise it is close to zero, then it means a more history-based prediction. HES involves the trend components, which is the long-term changing of the data (i.e. a slope), its parameter called *beta*, and it is an additional smoothing factor. Last but not least, WES takes into account the seasonality of the data, which reflects a cyclical repeating pattern. It comes with the parameter *gamma*, and similarly it is responsible for smoothing of the seasonal component. This component also requires a parameter *period* that is actually just the length of the historical data which we take for seasonality. These three parameters are combined to be called the HW Method. Two more parameters are needed, called *type* both for trend and seasonality, which can be set to additive or multiplicative, depending on whether the trend and the seasonality are linear or exponential, respectively. The additive means that all variables in the time series are simply summed to produce a forecast. In the multiplicative model instead of addition, multiplication is used to forecast.
- Random Forest (RF) is an ensemble of decision trees to generate the predicted value of a series. The first parameter is the *number of trees*, which are independent, and the data distributed for each tree is selected randomly from the dataset. The next step is decision making, where each decision tree makes an individual decision based on the input data. The last step is aggregation, where we calculate an average value based on the results of the decision trees to get the predicted values. The RF also comes with the parameter *lag* to reflect the length of the historical data and the parameter *depth*, which controls the size of the tree to avoid overfitting.
- Linear Regression (LR) is a simple way to predict future values, it assumes a linear relationship between the data to be predicted and the already available data, thus it plots a line by minimising squared error between them.
- Support Vector Regression (SVR) is based on a Support Vector Machine (SVM) classification algorithm, but can also be applied to regression tasks. The SVM method is used to find a hyperplane for a classification task, which separates the training data into classes. With SVR, the concept is very similar, but here we are looking for a hypersurface on which the training data fits the best. SVR can also handle non-linear data using a kernel function, namely RBF (Gaussian), Sigmoid or Polynomial, which maps the training data to a higher dimension.
- Finally, we also implemented a neural network-based solution, the LSTM, which is dedicated for time series analysis. LSTM is capable of remembering long time series easily, whilst other neural networks can only remember short-term information.

LSTM is based on RNN. An LSTM neural network is made up of specially designed cells, each cell has gates called forget, input and output gates, which decide what should happen with the information under processing. The LSTM cells have an internal state that carries the information. This state can be modified by the gates, for instance, they can modify, add or take away information from it. The decision, which information to leave from the cell state, is decided by the forget gate. The input gate is responsible for what new information to add to the state. Finally, the output gate, which is responsible for the internal state of the cell, decides which information to add from the state to the next LSTM cell. In our implementation, the following parameters are required by the LSTM network: the *loss function* is used for training, and is reduced by the model during the training process. Furthermore, *batch size* to determine the number of samples to deal with before updating the parameters of the model, and the *epoch size* to define how many times the learning algorithm works through the full training set are also needed. The size of the LSTM is determined by the *number of layers*, the *cells in a layer*, the *size of the input*, which are the amount of the lagged data, and *size of the output*, which is the amount of the prediction length. The *dropout* value is used to prevent overfitting, by defining the rate of randomly selected LSTM cells to be forgotten. Lastly, it also needs an *activation function* to decide whether the cells' value is important or not in the process, and an *Optimisation algorithm* that is used to update weights and biases.

The flow of the simulation extension can be seen in Figure 10, which consists of five steps. It is worth mentioning that these steps are executed by each IoT device and computing node separately; Step 1 is for devices, whilst Step 2-5 are for nodes.

Figure 10. The flow of the simulation including AI-based decision making and prediction

In Step 1, each IoT device produces data according to its predefined settings, which includes the size of measured data, the lifetime of a device and the data sampling interval. The produced data are forwarded to one of the fog nodes. On the computing nodes, either fog or cloud, tasks are formed from the incoming data in Step 2, and for each task a given amount of instructions (i.e. the length of the task, which is based on the amount of data to

be processed) are also associated to simulate the utilisation of resources. In Step 3, each node starts collecting those features, which are involved in the time series analysis (i.e. the not yet processed data).

To avoid the overhead of the offloading mechanism, our offloading mechanism works in a decentralised manner, therefore each node triggers the decision making algorithm, if the ratio of the not yet processed data and the maximum amount of bytes that a task can represent are greater than their predefined values in Step 4. This step contains Sub-step 4.1, 4.2, 4.3 and 4.4 as well. Our decision makers execute partial offloading, however it can be easily modified during the configuration of the simulation to work with fully offloaded tasks. In the case of the Pliant algorithm, we also take into account the time series analysis, where the data collected in Step 3 are used. Finally, in addition to tasks that are ready to be assigned to a virtual machine to be processed, the rest of the tasks are forwarded based on the output of the decision maker algorithm in Step 5. Besides that, a daemon service keeps scaling up and down the number of virtual machines for each node according to the actual load.

When the Pliant algorithm takes into account the possibility of using the predicted value, it can decide how exactly the predicted values are being involved in the decision making. For example, the decision maker can use values from the near future, or the far future or it can combine them as well. In this work, we use the average of near future values, because these values are usually more accurate.

Our previous experience with Pliant strategy was effective, when we used the following properties to construct the score value for each node: actual load of the resources, utilisation cost and unprocessed data. As we mentioned before, the score value indicates how seemingly good the decision is, so the higher value the algorithm gives, the more preferably the node is. In this work, we extend the score calculation of the algorithm with the predicted value with its error metrics to compare it to the actual unprocessed data. If the forecast value is less than the unprocessed data then the algorithm gives a strong value (close to 1), because it means that the node is not supposed to get too much data in the future.

4.1.1. Results

To measure the effectiveness and the differences of our offloading algorithms extended with various predictors, we evaluated a real-world IoT scenario with the DISSECT-CF-Fog simulator, which were inspired by and operated based on an existing meteorological service [19], where weather stations measure the atmosphere; its temperature, humidity, wind speed and direction, and so on. To be as realistic as possible, we positioned the fog and cloud nodes in Hungarian cities, and the location of IoT devices is also positioned nearby them, as depicted in Figure 11. In this example, only 20 IoT devices are shown, but during the evaluation we scaled up the number of active devices to 2000, and then to 4000.

Figure 11. The multi-layered Cloud-to-Edge system with IoT devices positioned in Hungary

Furthermore, during the five-hours long simulation, these devices work periodically, as follows. In the first hour, only two devices run, then we scale the number of devices up to six until the end of the second hour. In the next hour, only three devices, whilst in the fourth hour seven devices are operated. In the last, fifth hour we return to the original state, thus only two devices generate load for computing nodes. To evaluate this periodic behaviour of IoT devices on larger-scale as well, we are able to evenly scale up the number of devices running in every hour. To represent realistic communication delay between a device and a computing node, the average 4G latency (50 ms) is applied, plus it is weighted proportionally to the Euclidean distance.

To avoid the bottleneck-effect of the cloud data centre in case of high amount of IoT devices, we also applied clustering in the multi-layered fog topology: in Figure 11, *fog1* suffix denotes fog nodes having the weakest computing power (16 CPU cores and 32 GB RAM), *fog2* means the fog cluster head (32 CPU cores, 64 GB RAM), and finally, there is only one *cloud* with 520 CPU cores and 7680 GB RAM. The capacity of the cloud node mimics the HUN-REN Cloud schema (formerly known as ELKH Cloud) [20]. Figure 11 also presents the connections among the computing nodes (green lines) and the communication delay (i.e. latency) in ms (blue numbers), these connections determine where an overloaded node can forward the tasks to, in case of the offloading algorithm triggering. As it is also clearly seen in the figure that certain territories are not covered equally by the computing nodes (e.g. the area of Lake Balaton), which challenges the offloading algorithm

Different layers deal with different kinds of virtual machines (VMs), which were configured to work as instances of the AWS EC2 service. For example, VMs running on the cloud node require 8 CPU and 16 GB RAM (similarly as the *a1.2xlarge* instance does for 0.204\$ per hour). *fog1* nodes run with 4 CPU and 8 GB RAM for 0.102\$ hourly, and finally *fog2* halves the required resources, thus it deals with 2 CPU and 4 GB RAM for 0.051\$ hourly price.

The parameters, used for the simulation and for the prediction as well, are summarised in Table 5. It shows that an evaluation has numerous input variables, and their changes are able to affect the results. Therefore, in this work, we rather focused on synergizing the Fuzzy-based task offloading with the predictors in the simulation framework, and fixed the parameters as close as possible to a real cloud provider and meteorological service.

Parameters		Value
Offloading strategy	Task forwarding ratio	0.9
	Partial offloading (%)	50
	Pliant future values (pc.)	10
Device settings	Scaling multiplier	100, 200
	Base latency (ms)	50
	Data generation freq. (min.)	1
	Data size (byte)	150
Processing settings	Max. task size (kByte)	5
	Max. task length (min.)	4
Prediction configuration	Prediction length	64
	Test size	64
	Batch size	256
	Smoothing window size	48
	Smoothing polynomial degree	5
ARIMA	p, q, d	3, 0, 0
HW	Trend and Seasonal type	<i>Add</i>
	Alpha, Beta, Gamma	0.1
	Seasonal period	60
RF	Number of trees	10
	Max. depth	50
	Lags	100
LR	-	-
SVR	Kernel	<i>RBF</i>
LSTM	Loss function	<i>MSE</i>
	Epoch size	25
	Batch size	32
	Number of layers	4
	Cells in a layer	50
	Size of the input	256
	Size of the output	60
	Dropout	0.2
	Activation function	<i>Tanh, Sigmoid</i>
	Optimisation algorithm	<i>Adam</i>

Table 5. Parameters used for the simulation evaluation

These values were applied for two scenarios, first 2000 IoT devices utilised the computing architecture, then we doubled the number of active devices, thus 4000 IoT devices were operating. For each scenario, we applied 9 different offloading algorithms. The greedy *Push Up* and *Hold Down*, and then the *Pliant* strategy were considered as baselines, and to compare these to the extended, ML-assisted *Pliant* strategy. The LSTM network was trained using the results of the *Pliant* strategy with the 5 predictors added separately.

The evaluation results of the proposed ML-assisted task offloading algorithm are shown in Table 6 and Table 7. In each row, the blue background indicates the smallest, the red background denotes the largest value, if it exists. For the comparison, we take into account

the following outputs of the DISSECT-CF-Fog simulation environment: the *Timeout* value measures how much time is needed after the last IoT data fragment is forwarded to a computing node to be processed. A less effective configuration of the offloading mechanism may cause data congestion, therefore the less the *Timeout* is, the more real-time the application is. The *Runtime* measures how long the simulation runs on the host machine. The measurements were conducted using a PC equipped with Intel Core i7-3770 CPU @ 3.40GHz, 23 GB RAM and Ubuntu 20.04 operating systems.

Node Energy reflects the total energy consumption of the computing nodes (calculated based on the ELKH Cloud properties). *Utilisation Cost* was collected depending on the used AWS VM instances. These two characteristics of the simulation results are highly influenced by the offloading algorithm. As we mentioned before, the stronger VM instance a task utilises, the more energy is consumed and the more fee we must pay for it, therefore it matters how wisely the offloading algorithm chose. *Time on the Network* and *Data on the Network* also depend on the offloading decisions, they measure how much data was forwarded between the computing nodes all together, and how much time it took.

Finally, some statistical values are also available from the output, how many virtual machines were needed to process all data (*Number of VMs*), how many tasks were created based on that data (*Number of Tasks*), how many times the prediction algorithm was triggered during the evaluation (*Number of Predictions*), and finally, how large the average error of the three error metrics (MAE, MSE, RMSE) for each predictor was (*Average error of Predictions*).

As the results show, in many cases the *Push Up* and *Hold Down* strategies mean the upper and lower bounds. However, as Table 6 presents, the same execution time can be achieved (*Timeout* equals to 5) by applying the *Pliant with LR* algorithm for almost 2\$ cheaper. During the second scenario, as it is shown in Table 7, the *Pliant with ARIMA* strategy managed the task processing more efficiently from the aspect of execution time (*Timeout equals 94*), however it can be clearly seen that in the second scenario, due to the amount of IoT devices and their data, the computing nodes became overloaded. Nevertheless, in both evaluation cases (with 2000 and 4000 IoT devices), the *Pliant with LR / ARIMA* successfully reduced the execution time of the application, with fair usage of energy and costs.

Scaling multiplier	100								
Offloading strategy	Pliant	ARIMA	HW	Pliant with		SVR	LSTM	Push Up	Hold Down
				RF	LR				
Timeout (min.)	9	6	7	6	5	8	8	5	16
Runtime (sec.)	7	139	29	113	9	12	58	4	4
Node Energy (kWh)	42.4430	42.3919	42.4983	42.3664	42.2998	42.4214	42.3227	40.942	42.8018
Utilisation Cost (\$)	22.4399	22.4323	22.4340	22.3779	22.3983	22.4425	22.4255	24.1774	17.7956
Time on the Network (sec.)	46	46	46	46	46	47	46	39	84
Data on the Network (MB)	36	36	36	36	36	36	36	20	141
Number of VMs	82	82	82	82	82	82	82	82	63
Number of Tasks	3656	3653	3658	3659	3659	3650	3652	3623	3584
Number of Predictions	-	414	428	420	416	418	443	-	-
Average Error of Predictions	-	0.223	1.056	0.235	0.264	0.359	0.201	-	-

Table 6. Results of the simulation evaluation 2000 IoT devices

Scaling multiplier	200								
Offloading strategy	Pliant	ARIMA	HW	Pliant with		SVR	LSTM	Push Up	Hold Down
				RF	LR				
Timeout (min.)	101	94	99	98	98	97	101	243	421
Runtime (sec.)	11	276	35	130	13	16	60	7	7
Node Energy (kWh)	52.2389	51.7500	52.0986	52.0569	51.9911	52.0054	52.2093	62.0515	52.2643
Utilisation Cost (\$)	41.5038	41.3116	41.4434	41.4137	41.4120	41.4051	41.4732	45.8719	34.5227
Time on the Network (sec.)	58	59	58	59	58	59	58	52	149
Data on the Network (MB)	126	125	126	126	126	126	125	47	2457
Number of VMs	82	82	82	82	82	82	82	82	63
Number of Tasks	7049	7061	7051	7051	7052	7053	7055	7047	7008
Number of Predictions	-	439	457	452	455	482	442	-	-
Average Error of Predictions	-	0.233	0.635	0.251	0.216	0.311	0.235	-	-

Table 7. Results of the simulation evaluation with 4000 IoT devices

4.2. Simulation of the Urban Noise Classification Use Case

To provide a suitable environment for testing the various orchestration algorithms in Swarmchestrator, the simulator is further extended to model the behaviour of the demonstrators' applications. Although this implementation is currently in the early phase, it is envisioned to deploy the application in the simulator with the help of the newly introduced components described in Section 3. Thus, the runtime management of the application can also be simulated, to provide datasets based on the runtime characteristics for the various resource selection and runtime reconfiguration algorithms developed in WP1 and WP2.

The Urban Noise Classification application simulates a distributed system in which multiple Raspberry Pi 5 devices equipped with sound sensors perform localized audio data collection and preliminary signal processing. Each Raspberry Pi 5 unit is configured with 4 CPU cores, 4 GB of RAM, and a 32 GB SD card. The energy model accounts for minimum (2 W), idle (4 W), and maximum (15 W) power consumption levels.

Audio recordings are collected every 10 seconds, resulting in individual file sizes of approximately 640 kB. To simulate real-world measurement inconsistencies, occasional recording gaps are introduced randomly. Data is transmitted over Wi-Fi networks, modelled with a latency of 5-10 ms and a bandwidth range of 50-120 Mbps.

Since Raspberry Pi devices may be exposed to environmental factors, such as direct sunlight, which can cause overheating, especially, as no active cooling can be provided, the simulator will incorporate a weather-dependent model. This model will consider whether the devices are located indoors or outdoors and whether they are exposed to sunlight. The forecasting module introduced in Section 4.1 will further enhance this aspect by predicting sunlight conditions. Additionally, the simulator will provide datasets to support training and fine-tuning the runtime algorithms developed for orchestration.

The DISSECT-CF-Fog simulation will replicate:

- Sensor node deployment and task execution across multiple Raspberry Pi nodes,
- Energy consumption modelling based on usage states,
- Environmental impacts on computation (e.g., sunlight, temperature),

- Task generation and data offloading behaviour.

5. Modelling ACO-based Decentralised Orchestration

Although centralised solutions are robust for certain types of applications, they become less viable for next-generation IT services due to networking bottlenecks, latency issues, and the increasing need for real-time processing. As a result, decentralised computing paradigms might offer more flexible solutions for application management in terms of efficiency, scalability, and responsiveness, as well as services that are constrained in terms of connectivity and availability. In the decentralised and heterogeneous Cloud-to-Edge environment, where applications often deal with failures, loss of connectivity, and mobility, the orchestration service becomes essential, as it ensures seamless application delivery by handling complex tasks such as resource selection, deployment, monitoring, and runtime management in an automated manner. In decentralised application management, decisions are made by local orchestrators coordinating edge and fog nodes, based on their proximity. This allows them to make context-aware decisions about resource selection and task placement [21].

Physical proximity is an often used metric in large-scale and dynamic IoT environments, however, it might be insufficient in a highly heterogeneous environment. Consequently, logical proximity becomes more meaningful under such conditions. For instance, logical proximity clustering is used to dynamically group nearby smart devices into modules and logical spaces. These groupings are not based solely on physical location, but also on the functional relationship between devices and users, enabling more efficient resource management and seamless mobility support [22].

This section presents the modelling of a decentralised orchestration framework based on clustering techniques, which serves as a baseline for comparison with the Swarmchestrator solution. The results discussed in this section are part of a research work currently under review in *Simulation Modelling Practice and Theory* (SIMPAT) journal [3]. The framework operates by forming clusters coordinated by dedicated orchestrators, each representing a logical layer over the underlying physical infrastructure. These clusters are dynamically created at the time of application submission, ensuring that each application is managed by its own corresponding orchestrator. This design mitigates the limitations of a centralised orchestration approach, where a single orchestrator could become a bottleneck due to the need for continuously updated global knowledge about the system's state. Moreover, this architecture enhances fault tolerance: the failure of an individual orchestrator does not impact other applications or orchestrators within the system.

5.1. The Proposed Orchestration Framework

Metaheuristic algorithms are general-purpose approaches designed to solve a wide range of optimisation problems. They build on, or combine heuristic techniques to explore the solution space, they are able to avoid local optima, and iteratively refine results toward global solutions. Although running the algorithm can be computationally expensive, their flexibility makes them widely applicable across various problem domains.

Figure 12. The two-layered architecture of the proposed orchestration framework

Therefore, in this section, we present the adaptation of an ACO-based clustering algorithm originally proposed by Shelokar et al. [23]. The original algorithm was designed for general-purpose clustering, targeting high-dimensional datasets. For clarity and completeness, we include selected equations from the original problem formulation to explain the underlying algorithmic process. However, we extend and adapt the model to the context of application management within the Cloud-to-Edge continuum.

ACO is inspired by the behaviour of ants that find the shortest path to food sources. Artificial ants explore the solution space, depositing and following pheromones to guide the search. The method also accounts for pheromone evaporation, which prevents the algorithm from converging too quickly by iteratively reducing the influence of older paths. Although ACO is effective for combinatorial optimisation problems, its implementation requires careful parameter tuning. Too few ants reduce search diversity, increasing the risk of getting stuck in local optima, while too many ants increase computational costs and add noise to the pheromone matrix. Similarly, too few iterations may prevent convergence to the global optimum, while too many can lead to inefficiency.

At this point, we assume the presence of lightweight services running on each computing node in the system, enabling each to communicate with its neighbouring nodes. Furthermore, these services provide an application submission interface that allows any node to initiate the clustering process for an application.

Both approaches, the centralised clustering algorithm and the decentralised clustering method, rely on the underlying physical infrastructure and result in logically formed clusters. After the termination of any of our clustering algorithms, the most suitable cluster is selected from the multiple generated ones to host the application on its nodes. These nodes

provide the necessary resources for the dedicated orchestrator, which is solely responsible for managing the submitted application components. At this stage, it is worth mentioning that selecting the right cluster that fulfils the application's requirements is also a challenging task, and numerous ranking algorithms can be employed for such purposes. However, this task is beyond the scope of this work.

The proposed architecture is illustrated in Figure 12. The letters (A-F), forming a partially or fully connected network, represent any cloud, fog, and edge nodes that participate in the system. During the lifetime of the framework, they may belong to different logical groups at the same time. In other words, this work builds upon the concept of overlapping fog colonies, as introduced in [27], and extends it by integrating a centralised ACO-based clustering algorithm as well as a decentralised self-organising grouping mechanism. For instance, the resources of Node C are shared between the orchestrators of Application 1 and Application 2.

Table 8 lists the key notations and their meanings used in the description of the proposed clustering methods.

Notation	Description
$Node_1, \dots, Node_n$	n nodes to be clustered
$Cluster_1, \dots, Cluster_k$	k clusters consisting of nodes
<i>PheromoneMatrix</i>	$n \times k$ matrix of pheromone values storing cluster preferences
Ant_1, \dots, Ant_m	m ants searching for clustering solutions
<i>PheromoneIncrement</i>	Pheromone update based on a solution
<i>EvaporationRate</i>	Pheromone reduction factor per iteration
<i>Probability</i>	Decision threshold between exploitation and exploration
<i>Percentage</i>	Ratio of best ants' solutions considered for pheromone update
$Random_{Ant_j}$	A vector of n random numbers per iteration
$Solution_{Ant_j}$	A vector of length n storing the solution found by Ant_j
$Fitness_{Ant_j}$	The accumulated quality of the solution found by Ant_j
γ	Coefficient for controlling the cluster size
$Heuristic(Node_i, Node_l)$	Quality score for assigning $Node_i$ to $Node_l$
<i>Top</i>	Collection of ants with the best fitness values
$MaxFitness_{Top}$	The best fitness value among the ants in <i>Top</i>
$RelativeFitness_j$	The fitness of Ant_j relative to $MaxFitness_{Top}$
$GaussianKernel(x, h)$	A function used for weighting fitness values
ϵ	Random noise for stochastic update
T	Timeout threshold for cluster stability
\mathcal{N}_i	Neighbourhood of $Node_i$,

Table 8. Notations used for the centralised and the decentralised clustering

5.1.1. Centralised ACO-based Clustering

In the centralised approach, it is assumed that the decision-making component, the node that received the application submission, is responsible for dividing the computing resources into groups using the ACO algorithm and is directly connected to the elements participating in the clustering process. In other words, this version of the clustering algorithm is

particularly effective with a fully connected network to provide a large enough search space for the ACO. It is worth mentioning that although the clustering algorithm is centralised and relies on global information to form the clusters, the orchestration of the application is limited to the selected group of nodes. As a result, the overall system remains distributed in terms of application management.

It is also notable that this approach requires only the number of clusters (k) to be specified, rather than the initial centroids. Predefining centroids may limit the adaptability of the clustering algorithm and prevent it from finding the optimal grouping of computing resources, potentially leading to suboptimal performance at runtime. The goal of this ACO-based clustering is to assign each node ($Node_1, \dots, Node_n$) to a cluster such that the resulting groups represent an efficient division of resources according to the underlying criteria.

To achieve optimal clustering, the decision maker maintains and updates a global pheromone matrix during iterations of the ACO algorithm. The size of *PheromoneMatrix* is $n \times k$, and the highest pheromone value in the row indicates the cluster with which the node is associated at the end of the execution. For the sake of clarity, an example is also presented to demonstrate the execution of the algorithm. At first, each element of the matrix is initialised with random values chosen from the $[0.45, 0.55]$ interval. These numbers were determined based on empirical observations to avoid early convergence and support exploration, while random initialisation within the range also helps introduce slight diversity in the initial paths of the ants:

	<i>Cluster₁</i>	<i>Cluster₂</i>	<i>Cluster₃</i>
<i>Node₁</i>	0.45	0.52	0.55
<i>Node₂</i>	0.54	0.53	0.55
<i>Node₃</i>	0.48	0.51	0.50
<i>Node₄</i>	0.46	0.45	0.49

Once the execution of the ACO clustering is triggered, it requests information from its neighbours via messaging. The responses contain data that are used to measure the proximity between the computing resources. In other words, this information helps to calculate the heuristic value of the ACO algorithm to assess the quality of the solution found by the ants.

Therefore, the decision maker requires additional parameters. It is also necessary to specify how many ants (Ant_1, \dots, Ant_m) are searching for a separate solution.

The *PheromoneIncrement* value is used to increment the corresponding values of the pheromone matrix according to the quality of the solution found by the ants. It is also necessary to specify the rate of evaporation (*EvaporationRate*) for the same matrix, which reduces all elements of the matrix when an iteration ends. The decision maker also expects a *Probability* value, which will be used either to exploit (i.e., using the known paths) or to explore (i.e., discovering new paths) the search space with the ants. Lastly, the algorithm can

be limited in terms of the *Percentage* of ant solutions ranked according to the heuristic value, which will be considered when updating the pheromone matrix.

After the initialisation of the pheromone matrix, the iterative sequence of steps begins with new ants instantiated at the start of each iteration. Each ant uses two vectors of length n in the given step, where n refers to the number of nodes to be clustered. The $Random_{Ant_j}$ vector stores floating-point numbers randomly drawn from the interval $[0, 1]$ via uniform sampling, while the $Solution_{Ant_j}$ vector holds the solution found by the ant, which is represented by integer numbers from the interval $[1, k]$, where k refers to the number of clusters.

To find a solution, each ant uses one of two methods: exploitation or exploration. Each value of $Random_{Ant_j}$ is compared to the value of *Probability* for every i from 1 to n . If $Random_{Ant_j}[i] < Probability$, the exploitation phase is executed so that the centroid having the highest value in the i -th row of the pheromone matrix determines the cluster of $Node_i$.

Otherwise, in the exploration step, the ant selects a centroid based on a weighted random choice using the pheromone values of the corresponding row. First, the sum of all the pheromone values in the i -th row is calculated. Then another random number is generated from the $[0, sum]$ interval via uniform sampling. Finally, the algorithm iterates through the row, accumulating the values until the cumulative sum exceeds the random number. The index of the actual position is selected as the cluster for $Node_i$. To illustrate this process, an example of an ant's $Random_{Ant_j}$ vector is provided:

$$[0.35 \quad 0.85 \quad 0.29 \quad 0.65]$$

Let us suppose that *Probability* equals 0.7. This means that for the first, third, and fourth positions, the exploitation step will be executed, thus the index of $Cluster_i$ having the highest pheromone value in the global *PheromoneMatrix* will be selected for the solution. However, for the second position, the algorithm executes the exploration phase with a newly created random number (drawn from the $[0, sum]$ interval), which should be equal to 0.6 in this example. Since this random number is greater than the first value but less than the second value of the *PheromoneMatrix*'s second row, thus $Cluster_2$ will be chosen. As a result, the ant generated the following $Solution_{Ant_j}$ vector:

$$[3 \quad 2 \quad 2 \quad 3]$$

For each solution found by the ants, a fitness value is calculated using heuristic information. For this calculation, any physical or logical proximity can be considered, which measures the quality of the solution (e.g. distance, latency, or resource availability). The function evaluates the quality of a clustering solution by calculating the average pairwise heuristic distance between all nodes within each cluster, which appears in the numerator. In the denominator, the coefficient represents the number of unordered node pairs in the given cluster. To deal with the impact of the cluster size, this average is then multiplied by the cluster's cardinality raised to the power of *gamma*. This term introduces a penalty: smaller values of *gamma*

allow larger clusters to emerge more easily, while higher values increasingly penalise larger clusters:

$$Fitness_{Ant_j} = \sum_{c=1}^k \left(\frac{\sum_{i=1}^{|Cluster_c|} \sum_{l=i+1}^{|Cluster_c|} Heuristic(Node_i, Node_l)}{\binom{|Cluster_c|}{2}} \right) \cdot |Cluster_c|^\gamma$$

In order to exclude ants with too poor fitness value, the algorithm first sorts the ants by their fitness value, and only the first *Top* ants (i.e., the collection of ants with the best fitness values) are taken into account (according to *Percentage*) when updating the pheromone matrix. The algorithm then selects the ant with the best fitness value for normalisation. In this work, our solution looks for the minimum fitness value within the *Top* collection:

$$MaxFitness_{Top} = \frac{1}{Min_{a \in Top}(Fitness_a)}$$

After that, the relative fitness of the rest of the ant is calculated:

$$\forall i \in \{1, \dots, |Top|\} \quad RelativeFitness_i = \frac{MaxFitness_{Top}}{Fitness_{Top_i}}$$

The next step is that the global pheromone matrix is updated by increasing the pheromone level for each node according to the solutions of the *Top* ants:

$$\forall i \in \{1, 2, \dots, |Top|\}, \forall j \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\} \\ PheromoneMatrix_{j, Solution_{Top_i}[j]} += \\ PheromoneIncrement \cdot RelativeFitness_{Top_i}$$

The last step of the iteration is the pheromone evaporation process, during which all entries in the global pheromone matrix are updated:

$$\forall i \in \{1, 2, \dots, k\}, \forall j \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\} \\ PheromoneMatrix_{i,j} \cdot= (1 - EvaporationRate)$$

After the algorithm terminates, the cluster assignment for each node is determined by the index of the maximum pheromone value in its corresponding row of the *PheromoneMatrix*.

5.1.2. Decentralised Self-organising Clustering

Compared to the previously presented centralised approach, the decentralised self-organising clustering does not rely on a central coordinator and works even without a

fully connected network. Nodes that have limited connectivity can also participate in the decision-making process based on local information and communication with nearby peers. This structure is also useful in cases where some nodes cannot directly reach a central entity, for example, due to device mobility or security reasons. Furthermore, if the central entity fails in a centralised system, the entire clustering process may collapse. In contrast, the decentralised approach is more reliable: if a node fails, it does not necessarily affect the clustering, as other nodes can proceed with the clustering independently, resulting in the system having fault tolerance.

Although the presented decentralised algorithm does not strictly follow the ACO method, it incorporates certain ACO-inspired elements, such as stochastic decision-making and local interactions. Therefore, the ACO terminology is used throughout this section for consistency and simplicity.

Similarly to the centralised approach, the application is submitted to one of the nodes. Its role is to initiate the flooding process that triggers the self-organisation of the nodes. During flooding, a node sends a message to all of its neighbours, and each neighbour forwards the message to all of their neighbours recursively except the one from which it received the message.

Due to this decentralised structure, it is not feasible to create a central or global pheromone matrix, nor is the definition of cluster centroids necessary. When an application request is received from $Node_i$, the resource will maintain its own pheromone vector ($Solution_{Node_i}$), whose length is equal to the number of nodes. This vector presents the cluster preference scores of $Node_i$, where the index with the highest score indicates the node with which $Node_i$ intends to form a cluster. We also denote special positions in the pheromone vector: the i -th element of it is less than zero for $Node_i$ (meaning it cannot be clustered with itself), and any other element $Solution_{Node_i}[s]$ ($s \neq i$) has a positive value representing the preference for $Node_s$ if there is a link between $Node_s$ and $Node_i$. Otherwise, the given value equals zero.

This approach also deals with *Probability* to separate the exploitation and exploration phases and (*EvaporationRate*) to reduce all elements of the solution vector when an iteration ends. However, due to the decentralised nature, these parameters might be configured independently for every node.

First, a random number from the $[0, 1]$ interval is generated (via uniform sampling), which is then compared to *Probability*, determining whether the exploitation or exploration phase is executed. In the exploitation phase, the algorithm calculates the heuristic values for each neighbour of $Node_s$. Since the complexity of the clustering problem is slightly reduced (i.e., looking for the closest neighbour most proximate to $Node_i$), we consider all solutions instead of selecting only the best ones. Each element of the *Solution* vector is updated using a value generated by a Gaussian kernel function. The Gaussian kernel is a bell-shaped weighting function that assigns higher weights to values close to a given reference point and lower weights to those farther away. Using a Gaussian kernel also helps keep the values stable by converting heuristic distances into a limited range, so extreme latencies do not have too much influence on the update:

$$GaussianKernel(x, h) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}h} \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{x}{h}\right)^2\right)$$

In this case, the fitness value of $Node_i$ and $Node_s$ is the reference point that reflects how similar they are, which will be the first input of the kernel function, denoted by x . The second input is the parameter h , which controls how quickly the weight drops as the proximity value changes. If h is small, only very similar nodes get high weights. If h is large, even the least similar nodes can still have some influence.

$$\forall s \in \{1, 2, \dots, |neighbours|\}$$

$$Solution_{Node_i}[s] += GaussianKernel(Heuristic(Node_i, Node_s), h)$$

if $i \neq s$

Otherwise, in the case of exploration, we slightly modify the pheromone values using a small random factor based on the evaporation rate. This introduces controlled randomness into the preference values, which is especially useful when several neighbouring nodes have very similar fitness scores. This is ensured by drawing *epsilon* from a uniform distribution. In such cases, the exploration step encourages the discovery of alternative clustering options.

$$\forall s \in \{1, 2, \dots, |neighbours|\}$$

$$Solution_{Node_i}[s] = (1 - EvaporationRate) \cdot Solution_{node_i}[s] + \epsilon$$

if $i \neq s$

In the next step, after the final iteration of the simplified ACO, the nodes perform asynchronous message passing with each other to integrate local information into clusters. At the beginning of the process, each node is considered a distinct cluster. The goal of each node is to expand its group by joining the adjacent node that has the highest pheromone concentration in its local solution vector. Whenever a node receives a request, it compares its local cluster with the received one. If the two clusters differ, the nodes that appear in only one of the two sets will be notified about the new merged cluster structure.

Eventually, the information about the common cluster is propagated to all nodes. However, due to parallel and asynchronous communication, it is critical to determine when a cluster can be considered stable. In this work, we define the stability of the cluster using a parameter T , which represents the duration that a node waits without receiving any new cluster messages. A longer waiting time can slow down the algorithm and thus the deployment of the application, while a shorter time can lead to incorrect clustering, where some nodes in a cluster are still unaware of other members.

Several strategies can be considered to determine T . An option is to set a fixed timeout based on the expected network load. However, this approach requires prior knowledge of the network and its components. Alternatively, the waiting time can be dynamically adjusted at runtime, based on factors such as the average message delay.

Once a cluster considers itself stable (i.e., none of the nodes receives any new message within its T time), the cluster members select an orchestrator. The orchestrator might be selected based on the lexicographical order of node identifiers. The elected node becomes responsible for hosting the orchestrator component, which manages the deployment and execution of the application within the cluster. Before deployment, the final task of the orchestrator node is to notify the original requesting node (i.e., the one where the application was submitted) about the successfully formed cluster because, in the case of multiple groups of nodes created, the most suitable one should also be selected for the application.

Since each node connects to the neighbour with the highest similarity, the resulting intra-cluster topology naturally forms a minimum spanning tree (MST) structure, where nodes are connected through the least-cost links based on the heuristic metric. The MST is a classical graph theory problem, where the goal is to connect all nodes of a weighted undirected graph using the minimum total edge weight, while avoiding cycles. In distributed systems, the challenge lies in building such a tree using only local information and communication with neighbouring nodes [25].

Although the proposed algorithm does not solve the distributed MST problem, it forms tree-like, decentralised structures within clusters based on local decisions. These structures approximate the behaviour of spanning trees, optimised according to local proximity. As a practical outcome, if proximity is defined solely in terms of network latency, the resulting cluster topology naturally minimises internal communication delays, making it well-suited for latency-sensitive applications.

To illustrate the algorithm, consider the network presented in Figure 13. In this example, the application is submitted to Node D, which triggers the rest of the nodes in the network to start their clustering mechanism for the given application. After identifying the most proximate neighbour, highlighted in red in the figure, each node initiates its own solution set, representing a potential cluster. Messaging is carried out in a decentralised manner, which in this case resulted in five steps.

In Steps 1 and 2, Nodes C and B exchange their cluster information as they prefer each other. However, when a message from Node A is received by Node C, their clusters are merged, and two new messages are generated: the first is sent to Node B to inform it about Node A joining the group, while the second is sent to Node A to inform it about Node B. During this time, neither Node A nor Node B receives any additional messages indicating the presence of a new node. Therefore, after a timeout of T , the cluster consisting of Node A, B, and C is considered stable. Finally, Node C notifies Node D that a cluster is available for the application.

Figure 13. The process of the self-organising clustering with messages

5.1.3. Results

To evaluate and measure the effectiveness of the aforementioned approaches, we implemented the clustering algorithms and the evaluation framework in DISSECT-CF-Fog.

To represent applications in the simulation environment, we consider a workflow-based description of computing jobs, where the jobs and their connections (i.e., dependencies) are represented as a directed acyclic graph (DAG). The workflow consists of 100 jobs, with a total data transfer of approximately 19 GB, and follows the structure of the Cybershake [25], which is a well-known scientific workflow used in earthquake science to model and simulate ground motion for a given geographic region.

As mentioned earlier, regardless of whether the centralised or decentralised clustering algorithm is used, the decision-making node should rank the available clusters and select the most suitable one for application deployment. However, in this work, we focus on demonstrating the effectiveness of the clustering. Therefore, the same CyberShake application is submitted to each formed cluster for execution.

Another simplification in the evaluation is that we do not model the dynamic selection of virtualised resources with different capacities (e.g., small, medium, or large VMs). Instead, we assume that each computing component (i.e., virtual machine or container) is instantiated with a fixed configuration of 1 CPU core and 1 GB RAM, regardless of whether the corresponding node belongs to the cloud, fog, or edge layer. This means that even resource-constrained fog and edge devices (represented, e.g., by smartphones and Raspberry Pis) can host up to four virtualised resources for executing jobs. This decision was

made to focus on the effectiveness of the clustering algorithms. However, to be as realistic as possible, we use a model of a real cloud infrastructure, namely HUN-REN.

As was also discussed earlier, the task of the orchestration service is to monitor the state of the application and its execution environment after the deployment and, if needed, customise it with scaling and task scheduling, and, in general, improve the running of the application in an automated manner. Thus, once the group of nodes is determined for the orchestrator, the submitted application components, which are the workflow jobs in our case, are deployed to the selected nodes using the well-known Round-Robin policy. Once the tasks are associated with the nodes, each node maintains a local queue that holds only the tasks that have no remaining dependencies.

In the next step, when a job is ready for execution, the least loaded virtual machine is selected based on the number of jobs already submitted which are processed in FIFO order. Thus, for each orchestrator, a scaling policy is also introduced. The applied scaling strategy monitors the workload on each computing node within the cluster by evaluating the number of virtual machines currently running and the active jobs being processed on each node. If the number of jobs per virtual machine exceeds one, an additional virtual machine is provisioned to handle the increased load. Otherwise, if the job-to-VM ratio is equal to or less than one, the VMs running in idle state (i.e., they do not perform any job) will be shut down. This approach ensures that resource usage remains adaptive and efficient throughout the application lifecycle.

To measure the effectiveness of clustering algorithms, we calculate the Average Pairwise Distance (APD) of a cluster. A lower value indicates that the points within the cluster are closer to each other, implying a more coherent cluster structure. It is computed by calculating the average distance between all pairs of points in the cluster:

$$APD = \frac{1}{|C|} \sum_{i \in C} \sum_{j \in C, j \neq i} d(x_i, x_j)$$

Where C represents the cluster, $d(x_i, x_j)$ is the distance between the points x_i and x_j , and $|C|$ is the number of points in the cluster.

During the evaluation, we consider a European-wide scenario, where 20 cloud, fog, and edge nodes are placed on the continent. In our clustering methods, the heuristic value that influences the transition probability between nodes is based on the estimated network latency between them. In the simulation environment, network latency is closely associated with physical distance, reflecting the assumption that geographically closer nodes typically provide lower communication delays. This approach tries to address the main characteristic of edge and fog infrastructures, where topological and geographic proximity is often proportional to transmission overhead.

The detailed parametrisation of the evaluation scenario is presented in Table 9. The values, especially those related to the clustering algorithm, were selected based on preliminary

experiments to achieve stable behaviour and reliable performance during the actual simulation.

General parameters	
Cloud capacity	3 x 520 CPU cores and 640 GB RAM
Fog capacity	12 x 16 CPU cores and 32 GB RAM
Edge capacity	5 x 4 CPU cores and 4 GB RAM
Network latency	min: 17 ms, max: 317 ms
Cloud bandwidth	10 Gbps
Fog bandwidth	2 Gbps
Edge bandwidth	500 Mbps
VM configuration	1 CPU cores and 1 GB RAM (0.102 EUR hourly)
Cloud node energy	min: 20 idle: 143.5 max: 535.6
Fog node energy	min: 20 idle: 296 max: 493
Edge node energy	min: 1 idle: 3.5 max: 7.5
Centralised ACO clustering	
Pheromone matrix init values	min: 0.45 max: 0.55
Number of ants	50
Number of iterations	200
Probability	0.5
Percentage of top ants	0.2
Pheromone increment	0.15
Evaporation rate	0.3
Coefficient γ	1.5
Decentralised self organising clustering	
Pheromone vector init values	min: 0.45 max: 0.55
Number of ants	50
Number of iteration	200
Probability	0.75
Evaporation rate	0.15
Cluster stability time (min.)	1
Bandwidth of the Gaussian kernel (h)	1500
Noise ϵ	min: -0.01 max: 0.01

Table 9. Experimental settings for simulation

To evaluate the efficiency of the proposed centralised and decentralised clustering algorithms presented, we also consider the PAM (Partitioning Around Medoids) algorithm, which performs k-medoids clustering. This technique is often applied in the context of Edge Computing [26] and is similar to the well-known k-means clustering algorithm. In this work, it serves as a baseline for comparison with our proposed grouping methods. Thus, in the evaluation scenario, five use cases are defined to analyse and compare the proposed framework and clustering algorithms, as follows:

- A single large cluster (including all nodes) processes one submitted application,
- A single large cluster processes four simultaneously submitted applications,
- Four PAM-based clusters with fixed centroids, each processing one application,

- Four clusters created with the ACO centralised algorithm, each processing one application, and
- Four clusters created with the self-organising method, each processing one application.

The positions of the nodes, as well as the configuration of the single large cluster, are shown in Figure 14. Node 2, 4, 7, 15, and 18 are considered edge devices, Node 0, 11, and 19 represent cloud resources, and the remaining nodes are considered fog nodes. Since the proposed solution relies on random numbers, each use case was executed five times and the average results are presented.

Figure 14. Node distribution in the single-cluster setup

It is worth mentioning that in the decentralised approach, the final number of clusters cannot be predetermined due to the self-organising nature of the algorithm. However, during the experimental phase, the emergence of 2 to 5 clusters was typically observed. Based on this, we chose to use four clusters in every use case for comparison. This means that for the PAM-based clustering, we initially set Node 4, 13, 15, and 18 as medoids, intentionally selecting them from the edge of the map. However, as can be seen in Figure 15, after three iterations the algorithm converged to new medoids: Node 4, 5, 7, and 9. In

addition, an example of the centralised ACO grouping is shown in Figure 16, while Figure 17 illustrates a representative outcome of the self-organising approach.

Figure 15. The established clusters of the PAM approach with the final medoids

The simulation results of the four aforementioned use cases are presented in Table 10 and 11. For comparison, we consider the following metrics as follows. The *Cost* calculation in the simulator follows the pay-as-you-go billing, thus, the total running time of the virtual machines utilised by the particular application is counted, and then it is multiplied by the hourly price of the VM. The *Energy Consumption* is calculated based on the storage, network, or CPU utilisation of the physical layers (i.e., nodes). For this, the simulator considers constant energy consumption associated with the minimum energy power when the node runs but no active work is under execution, and dynamic energy consumption, when the node is actively working (e.g., it hosts numerous virtual machines). In the latter case, a linear interpolation is calculated based on the idle and maximum power of the node.

The *Utilised VMs* is a statistical metric reflecting the maximum number of virtual machines used during execution. It is worth noting that this value does not mean the VMs running at the same time but the total number of VMs requested by the orchestrators according to their VM scaling policy. The *Time on Network* and the *Bytes on Network* are two of the main

metrics to determine how efficient the resulting clustering is, as they denote how many bytes were transferred between the nodes on the network, and how much time the transfers needed during the runtime. The *Execution time* refers to the time interval between the start of the first job and the completion of the last job for a given application.

Figure 16. The established clusters with the centralised ACO approach

Clusters can also be compared based on the *Cluster APD*, defined as the average pairwise distance among the nodes in a given cluster. The *Messages for Clustering* sums up the total messages needed to create the clusters, and the *Nodes in the Cluster* presents how many nodes are selected to be in the given cluster by the clustering algorithm. In the latter case, it is worth mentioning that the self-organising clustering algorithm ensures that a node always finds a cluster, thus, a cluster consisting of only a single node cannot be created. In the case of centralised clustering, a cluster can contain only one node (i.e. centroids) if none of the ants prefers that direction of the clustering. However, the single-node setup might be critical due to the risk of a single point of failure.

During the evaluation, we performed the five use cases mentioned above in the topology presented in Figure 14 to compare the results and justify the significance and effect of the chosen clustering algorithm. As mentioned earlier, ranking the formed clusters to identify

the most suitable one for the given application is beyond the scope of this work. Therefore, the same application was submitted to each cluster.

First, we examine the impact of the different clustering strategies by highlighting the best-performing cluster in terms of application execution time. Accordingly, Table 10 presents the performance metrics of the selected clusters.

The results show that both decentralised and centralised clustering approaches are effective for latency-sensitive applications. In particular, the self-organising clustering achieved the lowest APD of 471.55 km, while the centralised ACO-based approach also performed well with 530.93 km. These values are significantly lower than the PAM-based clustering (590.40 km) and the single-cluster baseline (1,379.34 km). Since the clustering is based on physical proximity, which correlates with network latency in our setup, lower APD values indicate better communication efficiency within the cluster.

Similar trends can be observed in the network metrics. The centralised cluster had the shortest time spent on network communication (324 seconds), while the decentralised cluster achieved 655 seconds, both outperforming the single-cluster setup (849 seconds) and the PAM-based cluster (820 seconds), despite handling similar data volumes (approximately 16–19 GB).

Metrics	Single Cluster (1 App)	PAM-based Clusters (1 App)	Centralised Clusters (1 App)	Decentralised Clusters (1 App)
Cost (EUR)	0.14	0.20	0.21	0.19
Energy Consumption (kWh)	0.67	0.38	0.36	0.30
Utilised VMs (pc.)	24	17	15	20
Time on Network (seconds)	849	820	324	655
Bytes on Network (MB)	18,990	16,711	16,467	16,405
Execution Time (minutes)	7.0	11.0	10.0	9.0
Cluster APD (km)	1,379.34	590.40	530.93	471.55
Nodes in the Cluster (pc.)	20	7	6	5

Table 10. Simulation results of use cases 1, 3, 4, and 5

In terms of application execution time, the decentralised and centralised clusters performed better than the PAM-based solution, with 9.0 and 10.0 minutes, respectively, compared to 11.0 minutes for PAM. Although the single-cluster baseline achieved the fastest execution (7.0 minutes), this was mainly due to its access to all 20 nodes and 24 virtual machines, which allowed for more effective scalability.

However, using fewer nodes has its own advantages. With only 5 or 6 nodes involved in each cluster when using the proposed clustering algorithms, data dependencies between tasks can be handled more efficiently. When dependent jobs are deployed on the same node,

inter-node data transfers can be mitigated, which helps to reduce communication overhead on the network.

Furthermore, all clustering approaches were able to reduce the energy consumption compared to the single-cluster setup (0.67 kWh). This was especially true for the decentralised clustering, which reduced energy usage by more than 50%. This higher consumption in the single-cluster case was caused by the use of all cloud and fog nodes, which typically have higher power demand. However, it is important to note that this distribution was not directly controlled by the clustering algorithms in the current experiment.

Overall, the experiment confirms that latency-aware clustering, especially in its decentralised form, can significantly reduce the communication overhead, while maintaining good performance even with a limited number of nodes.

To demonstrate the overall behaviour of the system, Table 11 compares the performance of four applications executed simultaneously under different clustering approaches.

Managing all four applications within a single global cluster or using PAM-based clustering resulted in poorer performance in terms of average execution time (14.0 minutes and 12.5 minutes, respectively), compared to the proposed methods (12.5 and 12.0 minutes). A similar trend can be observed in network communication time, where the single cluster and PAM setup needed 725 and 649 seconds on average, while the centralised and decentralised clusters reduced this to 515 and 607 seconds, respectively. These results clearly show that network communication plays a significant role in the operation of the whole framework.

Metrics	Single Cluster (4 Apps)	Centralised Clusters (4 Apps)	Decentralised Clusters (4 Apps)
Total Cost (EUR)	0.84	1.02	1.01
Total Energy Consumption (kWh)	1.24	1.45	1.24
Utilised VMs (pc.)	76	62	72
Average Time on Network (seconds)	725	647	424
Average Bytes on Network (MB)	17,929	14,687	13,694
Average Execution Time (minutes)	14.0	13.75	11.75
Average Cluster APD (km)	1,379.34	761.60	756.73
Messages for Clustering (pc.)	0	38	83

Table 11. Simulation results of use cases 2, 3, 4, and 5

The proposed clustering approaches successfully mitigated this communication overhead by forming tighter node groups, as indicated by their lower APD (746.13 km and 676.30 km),

compared to the baselines (1,379.34 km and 752.53 km). Furthermore, the self-organising clustering algorithm was able to provide the shortest average execution time at the system level at 12.0 minutes.

Regarding energy consumption and the number of utilised virtual machines, the differences between the methods were relatively small. This can be attributed to the shared orchestration logic across all approaches, which applied the same Round-Robin scheduling and scaling policy. Nevertheless, the decentralised method again achieved the lowest energy usage (1.16 kWh), suggesting a slightly more efficient distribution of workload.

The only notable trade-off of the self-organising approach was the higher number of coordination messages (83) required for cluster formation. This reflects the increased overhead of decentralised coordination. However, the improvements in proximity, communication efficiency, and execution time clearly justify this additional effort, especially in distributed, latency-sensitive environments.

Figure 17. The established clusters with the self-organising approach

In summary, the proposed framework provides a stable basis for further research in decentralised orchestration to evaluate a wide range of orchestration algorithms for next-generation applications.

6. TOSCA Support in Simulation

To align with Swarmchestrator's goal of supporting TOSCA-based application descriptions, a crucial step is enabling the simulator to directly parse and execute application models from these standardised specifications. This integration will make sure our simulation environment accurately mirrors real-world deployment workflows. This way, we can easily test, validate, and fine-tune orchestration strategies using actual TOSCA definitions.

This section presents the initial approach regarding the use of TOSCA to define infrastructure requirements for simulation-based execution in DISSECT-CF-Fog. It starts from a general overview of the components of the TOSCA and DISSECT-CF-Fog simulator, where specific connections between them are described. Then, we outline the structure of a TOSCA-based YAML file that describes infrastructure requirements across the Cloud-to-Edge continuum. The section then explains how the file is parsed and used to execute a simulation. Initial findings suggest that TOSCA offers a structured and efficient method for describing Cloud-to-Edge infrastructure and applications, facilitating dynamic orchestration in complex environments.

6.1. TOSCA Description Language

TOSCA is an OASIS standardised description language that defines how cloud-based applications and infrastructure components are described, managed, and deployed [5]. TOSCA provides a consistent framework for defining the topology of complex cloud-based applications and their underlying infrastructure. The key elements of TOSCA are:

- *Node templates*. Define physical components (e.g., cloud and fog nodes, edge devices).
- *Capabilities*. Define the features or properties of a node (e.g., capacity, memory).
- *Requirements*. Define the dependencies or relationships between nodes.
- *Policies*. Define additional attributes related to deployment (e.g., performance, security).

These elements will be used in this initial approach to represent the nodes, their capacities, relationships, and performance policies. TOSCA structures the representation of Cloud-to-Edge systems using the YAML language. For example, a TOSCA-based description in YAML of a Cloud node with 2 CPU, 4GB of memory, and 100 GB of disk storage can be represented by the following code sample:

```

topology_template:
  node_templates:
    cloud_node_1:
      type: toska.nodes.Cloud
      properties:
        num_cpus: 2
        mem_size: 4 GB
        disk_size: 100 GB
    
```

Following a similar approach, fog nodes or edge devices can also be described, as well as their relationships with other nodes or devices (i.e., network relationship), and policies to define additional attributes. These descriptions will be detailed later in this document.

6.2. Describing Cloud-to-Edge Infrastructures and Applications with TOSCA

This subsection details how to interpret TOSCA-based descriptions for modelling infrastructure and application requirements across the Cloud-to-Edge continuum. In order to align TOSCA’s structured framework for describing infrastructure and application requirements with DISSECT-CF-Fog, the first step is to identify the relevant TOSCA elements that can be mapped to components in the DISSECT-CF-Fog simulator. The next step is to create a TOSCA-based YAML structure, which can then be parsed to execute a simulation in DISSECT-CF-Fog. This methodological process is summarised in Figure 18.

Figure 18. Methodology on matching TOSCA with DISSECT-CF-Fog

Table 12 summarises how each core TOSCA element is interpreted into the corresponding DISSECT-CF-Fog class or simulation parameter. After the table we expand on each mapping explanation spanning both on TOSCA and DISSECT-CF-Fog. Then, an example is given on how a TOSCA-based YAML description should be written, so that the DISSECT-CF-Fog parser instantiates exactly the desired objects.

TOSCA element	DISSECT-CF-Fog component	Description
node_templates → type	Computing Appliance (CA)	Each template represents one ComputingAppliance instance (i.e., cloud, fog, or edge node)
node_templates → properties/capabilities	Alterable Resource Constraints (ARC)	CPU, memory, disk size, bandwidth, and other attributes are defined as properties or capabilities for the TOSCA node, which are then mapped to corresponding fields in ARC
node_templates → requirements (groups)	Network topology links (i.e., parent or neighbour node)	For each requirement (in this case, groups) in TOSCA, the links or relationships are defined between nodes (CA), such as parent or neighbour
-	Instance	Defines VM instances for nodes, considering ARC + Virtual Appliance (VA) representing image files
Policies	Simulation logic and performance constraints	Defines performance and security constraints, and it brings custom attributes to the node (e.g., geolocation, communication range, and power)

Table 12. TOSCA and DISSECT-CF-Fog alignment of elements

In TOSCA, a typical topology template consists of:

- *Node_templates, type*. A *type* defines a node component (e.g., cloud, fog node and edge node) along with its expected *properties*, *capabilities*, and *requirements*. In DISSECT-CF-Fog, these can become instances of the ComputingAppliance class, which can further be distinguished by deployment tier (i.e., cloud, fog, edge) to model a physical or virtual node with given properties (e.g., geolocation, power profile, network bandwidth).

tosca.nodes.cloud -> *ComputingAppliance (cloud)*

tosca.nodes.fog -> *ComputingAppliance (fog)*

tosca.nodes.edge -> *ComputingAppliance (edge)*

- *node_templates, properties/capabilities*. Under each template description, TOSCA's properties/capabilities (e.g., *num_cpus*, *mem_size*, *disk_size*, *processing_per_core*) describe the resource envelope. In DISSECT-CF-Fog, these are represented by an AlterableResourceConstraints object, which encapsulates the same resource limits and describes what the ComputingAppliance can offer for a given virtualised resource.

osca.nodes.capabilities.cloud.num_cores -> AlterableResourceConstraints (num_cpus, ..)

tosca.nodes.capabilities.cloud.mem_size -> AlterableResourceConstraints (., mem_size, ..)

tosca.nodes.capabilities.cloud.processing_per_core -> AlterableResourceConstraints (., processing_per_core)

- *requirements/groups*. TOSCA's groups help to define how nodes are connected or how they depend on each other. Groups belong to the *requirements* subfield of TOSCA-based templates. These can be related in DISSECT-CF-Fog to the network topology links (parent-child or neighbour relationships) between ComputingAppliance instances. These link relationships can have extra detailed information such as latency and bandwidth.

tosca.groups.cloudnetwork.members → fog.setParent (cloud, latency)

tosca.groups.cloudnetwork.members → fog.setNeighbour (fog2, latency)

- *Instance*. Indicates the container image to run. In DISSECT-CF-Fog, an Instance object combines a VirtualAppliance (i.e., a VM/image file or container) with its AlterableResourceConstraints and deploys it on a ComputingAppliance, thereby forming a runnable unit in the simulation.
- *Policies*. In TOSCA these give higher-level constraints or behaviours both of the application and the infrastructure. For instance, they can define geographic locations, power profiling, scaling rules, or security requirements. In DISSECT-CF-Fog, for this parsing case, these properties can robust the attributes corresponding to ComputingAppliance, Instance, or AlterableResourceConstraints.

tosca.policies.cloudpolicy.properties.freq → ComputingAppliance (., range, ..)

tosca.policies.cloudpolicy.properties.latitude → ComputingAppliance (., latitude, ..)

tosca.policies.cloudpolicy.properties..longitude → ComputingAppliance (., longitude, ..)

The above explanations provide several references and approaches for creating TOSCA-based descriptions that meet DISSECT-CF-Fog simulation requirements. In the next subsection, a detailed TOSCA-based description example for a specific application infrastructure is presented.

6.2.1. Creating a TOSCA-based YAML file

Figure 19. An example architecture defined in DISSECT-CF-Fog

To represent a TOSCA-based description for a given Cloud-to-Edge infrastructure to be executed on DISSECT-CF-Fog, this section will start with an existing example of DISSECT-CF-Fog, which will be described using TOSCA. Figure 19 presents the architecture of the simulation to be executed in DISSECT-CF-Fog.

No	Node type	Characteristics	Connections
2	Cloud	Cloud Node 1 CPU cores: 2 Memory size: 4 GB Disk size: 100 GB	Cloud 1 network: Cloud Node 1, Fog Node 1, Fog Node 2
		Cloud Node 2 CPU cores: 2 Memory size: 4 GB Disk size: 100 GB	Cloud 2 network: Cloud Node 2, Fog Node 3, Fog Node 4
4	Fog	Fog Node 1 CPU cores: 2 Memory size: 4 GB Disk size: 50 GB	Fog 1 parent: Cloud Node 1 Fog 1 neighbour: Fog Node 2 Fog 1 network: Edge Device 1- 5
		Fog Node 2 CPU cores: 2 Memory size: 4 GB Disk size: 50 GB	Fog 2 parent: Cloud Node 1 Fog 2 neighbour: Fog Node 1 Fog 2 network: Edge Device 6 - 10
		Fog Node 3 CPU cores: 2 Memory size: 4 GB Disk size: 50 GB	Fog 3 parent: Cloud Node 2 Fog 3 neighbour: Fog Node 4 Fog 3 network: Edge Device 6 - 10

		Fog Node 4 CPU cores: 2 Memory size: 4 GB Disk size: 50 GB	Fog 4 parent: Cloud Node 2 Fog 4 neighbour: Fog Node 3 Fog 4 network: Edge Device 1 - 5
10	Edge Device	Edge Device 1 - 5 CPU cores: 2 Memory size: 2 GB Disk size: 4 GB	Edge Device network: Fog 1 network, Fog 4 network
		Edge Device 6 - 10 CPU cores: 2 Memory size: 2 GB Disk size: 4 GB	Edge Device network: Fog 2 network, Fog 3 network

Table 13. Characteristics of the Cloud-to-Edge infrastructure in DISSECT-CF-Fog

Table 13 reflects the basic elements of the infrastructure and networking. The characteristics can be described in TOSCA by *node templates*, *characteristics*, and *requirements* elements. The connections and network configuration can be expressed through the *groups* element of TOSCA. Additionally, certain specific characteristics are needed to execute the demo simulation, which in this case can be set using the *policies* element of TOSCA. Some of the required specific characteristics are detailed in Table 14.

Node Type (Name)		Characteristics
Cloud	Cloud Node 1	Latitude: 47.45; Longitude: 21.3; Range: 100; Start Up Process: 100.0; Processing Per Core: 0.001
	Cloud Node 2	Latitude: 42.71; Longitude: 21.8; Range: 52; Start Up Process: 100.0; Processing Per Core: 0.001
Fog	Fog Node 1	Latitude: 47.6; Longitude: 17.9; Range: 30; Start Up Process: 100.0; Processing Per Core: 0.001
	Fog Node 2	Latitude: 47.6; Longitude: 18.2; Range: 50; Start Up Process: 100.0; Processing Per Core: 0.001
	Fog Node 3	Latitude: 42.85; Longitude: 21.65; Range: 32; Start Up Process: 100.0; Processing Per Core: 0.001
	Fog Node 4	Latitude: 42.85; Longitude: 21.95; Range: 32; Start Up Process: 100.0; Processing Per Core: 0.001
Edge	Edge Device 1 to Edge Device 10	Max Input Bandwidth: 3,250; Max Output Bandwidth: 3,250; Disk Bandwidth: 3,250; Min Power: 0.065; Idle Power: 1.475; Max Power: 2.0; Disk Divider: 1.0; Network Divider: 2.0; Per Core Processing: 0.001

Table 14. Specific characteristics of the Cloud-to-Edge infrastructure in DISSECT-CF-Fog

Therefore, based on the characteristics shown in Table 13 and Table 14 of the DISSECT-CF-Fog example (see in Figure 17), the TOSCA-based YAML specification of this Cloud-to-Edge infrastructure is as follows:

- *TOSCA nodes definition.* The definition of the 2 cloud nodes, 4 fog nodes, and 10 edge devices should be structured as the following example of the *cloud_node_1*:

```

topology_template:
  node_templates:
    # Cloud Node 1
    cloud_node_1:
      type: tosca.nodes.Compute
      capabilities:
      host:
      properties:
        num_cpus: 2
        mem_size: 4 GB
        disk_size: 100 GB
      requirements:
        - cloud_network:
            node: cloud_network_1
    ... (--- description continues---)

```

- *TOSCA network definition.* The network definition is through the element *groups*, as the following example of *cloud_network_1* and *fog_network_1*:

```

groups:
  cloud_network_1:
    type: tosca.nodes.network.Network
    members: [cloud_node_1, fog_node_1, fog_node_2]
  fog_network_1:
    type: tosca.nodes.network.Network
    members: [fog_node_1, edge_device_1, edge_device_2, edge_device_3, edge_device_4, edge_device_5]

```

- *TOSCA policies definition.* The definition of policies is made for each node, as the following example of *cloud_node_1_policy*:

```

policies:
  cloud_node_1_policy:
    type: CloudNodePolicy
    targets: [cloud_node_1]
    properties:
      Application:
        freq: 2.5 GHz
        tasksize: 100 MB
        instructions: 5000
        ActivateRatio: 0.8
        TransferDivider: 4
      Instance:
        va:
          StartUpProcess: 100 ms
        arc:
          ProcessingPerCore: 0.001
          PricePerTick: 0.02
      ComputingAppliance:
        Geolocation:
          latitude: 47.45
          longitude: 21.30
        Range: 100 km

```

As shown in Figure 18, a TOSCA-based YAML file (containing infrastructure, specifications and features) is passed to a parser that translates its contents into DISSECT-CF-Fog parameters. In this workflow, the parser bridges the standardised TOSCA descriptors and the simulation engine. First, it reads the YAML template and extracts each node's type, properties, and networking requirements. Those elements are then mapped to corresponding Java objects, which are handed off to DISSECT-CF-Fog to drive the project-specific simulation. Once parsing is complete, the simulator uses those Java objects to build the network topology and launch the run.

Figure 20. Execution of the simulation process

Figure 20 illustrates this process in more detail. During initialization, the cloud, fog, and edge nodes are created as *ComputingAppliance* and *Instance* objects. Their resource capabilities and constraints (such as CPU, memory, and disk) come from *VirtualAppliance* and *AlterableResourceConstraints* mappings. At the same time, any execution policies (e.g., geolocation, power profiles) are applied via the *ComputingAppliance* and *arc* settings. Finally, DISSECT-CF-Fog executes the simulation with these configured nodes and links.

After parsing and running it in DISSECT-CF-Fog, the simulator produces the output summarised in Table 15, which confirms the successful execution of the Cloud-Edge scenario as defined by the TOSCA-based description.

Metric	Value
Total number of devices	10
Runtime (minutes)	80
Simulation duration (minutes)	703
Total energy consumption of nodes (kWh)	0.21551
Total energy consumption of IoT devices (kWh)	0.31849
Total cost (EUR)	19.3875
IoT costs by provider (EUR)	IBM: 0.00022 AWS: 0.00647 Azure: 1.62295
Data generated / received / processed / locally processed / stuck (bytes)	599,000 / 239,600 / 59,900 / 299,500 / 0
Total messages	5,990
Total network time (seconds)	14
Total network traffic (MB)	0
Number of VMs / tasks	5 / 1,231
Mobility events	Position changes: 6,510 Node changes: 6 Connects: 6 Disconnects: 2

Table 15. Simulation outputs

Conclusions & Next Steps

This deliverable has detailed ongoing works on the Swarmchestrate project over its first 18 months. The progress achieved has provided the initial framework for establishing a flexible and extensible simulation environment to be able to simulate the decentralised Swarmchestrate system and its application management lifecycles.

The DISSECT-CF-Fog simulator was extended towards modelling components that are related to application submission and the deployment phase in the decentralised environment. With the simulation tool, we proved that the initially proposed broadcasting algorithm is less viable due the overloaded communication channels. We successfully simulated the fine-tuned broadcasting algorithm and the resource offer ranking method and the process of swarm formation proposed by the partners to prove the adaptability of the proposed solution. The results were summarised in a conference paper [1] and presented in Section 3.

We also introduced a module supporting time-series analysis, and its ability was tested with a fuzzy-based offloading algorithm for IoT applications utilising fog and cloud nodes. This module can be utilised for implementing more sophisticated orchestration algorithms and to predict the behaviour of the demonstrators' applications before they are actually deployed. The achieved results were concluded in a conference paper [2] and presented in Section 4.

Next, the swarm-based clustering based on ACO technique for decentralised orchestration was presented. The proposed solution will be used to analyse alternative deployment strategies that help to enhance and fine-tune the proposed orchestration algorithm of Swarmchestrate. The results are summarised in a journal paper [3] currently under review, and presented in Section 5.

Finally, Section 6 describes our approach on synergizing TOSCA and DISSECT-CF-Fog. On the one hand, the use of TOSCA with the DISSECT-CF-Fog simulator has been successfully achieved by identifying the core elements that directly relate between these two. A first parsing and simulation approach was performed to demonstrate the feasibility of going from a TOSCA description to executing a simulation on DISSECT-CF-Fog. However, a significant challenge is that TOSCA's high-level performance attribute definitions are less sufficient for DISSECT-CF-Fog, which demands more granular specifications for network operations and computing node parameterization.

Overall, the work presented in this deliverable provides a solid foundation for fine-tuning the Swarmchestrate system through simulation. These efforts have also clearly demonstrated the viability of algorithms and methods proposed so far within the Project. Furthermore, these improvements help to further extend the simulation environment towards the concept of Digital Twin that will function as a dynamic, virtual replica of the actual Swarmchestrate ecosystem, enabling us to predict system behaviour, rigorously test and validate orchestration strategies, and optimize resource allocation in a controlled, risk-free environment prior to deployment.

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